
IC3 for Probabilistic Systems

by
Kevin Batz

Master's Thesis at RWTH Aachen University,
Lehrstuhl für Informatik 2

Submitted to: Fakultät für Mathematik, Informatik und
Naturwissenschaften der RWTH Aachen

Submission Date: May 16, 2019

First examiner: Prof. Dr. Ir. Dr. h. c. Joost-Pieter Katoen

Second examiner: Prof. Dr. Thomas Noll

Thesis advisers: Sebastian Junges, Dr. Benjamin Kaminski,
Christoph Matheja

Eidesstattliche Versicherung

Statutory Declaration in Lieu of an Oath

Batz, Kevin Stefan

332143

Name, Vorname/Last Name, First Name

Matrikelnummer (freiwillige Angabe)

Matriculation No. (optional)

Ich versichere hiermit an Eides Statt, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit/Bachelorarbeit/
Masterarbeit* mit dem Titel

I hereby declare in lieu of an oath that I have completed the present paper/Bachelor thesis/Master thesis* entitled

IC3 for Probabilistic Systems

selbstständig und ohne unzulässige fremde Hilfe (insbes. akademisches Ghostwriting) erbracht habe. Ich habe keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt. Für den Fall, dass die Arbeit zusätzlich auf einem Datenträger eingereicht wird, erkläre ich, dass die schriftliche und die elektronische Form vollständig übereinstimmen. Die Arbeit hat in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen.

independently and without illegitimate assistance from third parties (such as academic ghostwriters). I have used no other than the specified sources and aids. In case that the thesis is additionally submitted in an electronic format, I declare that the written and electronic versions are fully identical. The thesis has not been submitted to any examination body in this, or similar, form.

Ort, Datum/City, Date

Unterschrift/Signature

*Nichtzutreffendes bitte streichen

*Please delete as appropriate

Belehrung:

Official Notification:

§ 156 StGB: Falsche Versicherung an Eides Statt

Wer vor einer zur Abnahme einer Versicherung an Eides Statt zuständigen Behörde eine solche Versicherung falsch abgibt oder unter Berufung auf eine solche Versicherung falsch aussagt, wird mit Freiheitsstrafe bis zu drei Jahren oder mit Geldstrafe bestraft.

Para. 156 StGB (German Criminal Code): False Statutory Declarations

Whoever before a public authority competent to administer statutory declarations falsely makes such a declaration or falsely testifies while referring to such a declaration shall be liable to imprisonment not exceeding three years or a fine.

§ 161 StGB: Fahrlässiger Falscheid; fahrlässige falsche Versicherung an Eides Statt

(1) Wenn eine der in den §§ 154 bis 156 bezeichneten Handlungen aus Fahrlässigkeit begangen worden ist, so tritt Freiheitsstrafe bis zu einem Jahr oder Geldstrafe ein.

(2) Strafflosigkeit tritt ein, wenn der Täter die falsche Angabe rechtzeitig berichtet. Die Vorschriften des § 158 Abs. 2 und 3 gelten entsprechend.

Para. 161 StGB (German Criminal Code): False Statutory Declarations Due to Negligence

(1) If a person commits one of the offences listed in sections 154 through 156 negligently the penalty shall be imprisonment not exceeding one year or a fine.

(2) The offender shall be exempt from liability if he or she corrects their false testimony in time. The provisions of section 158 (2) and (3) shall apply accordingly.

Die vorstehende Belehrung habe ich zur Kenntnis genommen:

I have read and understood the above official notification:

Ort, Datum/City, Date

Unterschrift/Signature

Abstract

IC3 is a SAT-based model checking algorithm for verifying or refuting reachability properties of symbolically represented and finite transition systems: Given a finite transition system represented by means of propositional formulae and a set of target locations, is some target location reachable in the given transition system?

In this thesis, we investigate whether the fundamental concepts of IC3 can be employed for model checking *probabilistic* systems. As a first step, we identify these fundamental concepts. While existing presentations of IC3 depend on the fact that IC3 is an algorithm operating on symbolically represented transition systems, we develop a framework for model checking possibly infinite and explicitly represented transition systems via IC3. Using this framework, we then develop an IC3-style algorithm for the quantitative variant of reachability in Markov chains: Given a Markov chain \mathcal{C} , a set of goal states G , and a threshold probability λ , is the probability to eventually reach a state in G at most λ ? First, we focus on explicitly represented and finite Markov chains. We prove our algorithm sound and characterize its termination behavior. This algorithm requires a pre-computation of the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with probability 0. Since this can be infeasible for large or infinite Markov chains, we extend IC3 for Markov chains by an incremental, qualitative reachability analysis for computing (sufficient subsets of) $S_{=0}$ on-the-fly.

Furthermore, we have implemented our approach. Experimental evaluations show that IC3 for *explicitly represented* Markov chains is not efficient. Therefore, we discuss ideas on how to employ the concepts developed in this thesis for model checking *symbolically* represented Markov chains. Similar to the symbolic version of IC3 for finite transition systems, this enables so-called *generalization*. We consider a finite Markov chain obtained from a PRISM program as well as an infinite one obtained from a probabilistic pushdown automaton and show that generalization can increase the efficiency of our algorithm in both cases.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Preliminaries	7
2.1	Transition Systems	7
2.2	Probability Theory	11
2.3	Markov Chains	13
3	IC3 for Transition Systems	19
3.1	Reachability Problems	19
3.2	Algorithm and Specifications	22
3.3	Standard IC3	27
3.4	Standard Backward IC3	34
3.5	Soundness and Termination	37
4	IC3 for Markov Chains	41
4.1	Algorithm $IC3[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$	41
4.2	Soundness and Termination	55
4.3	Implementation and Experimental Evaluation	61
4.4	On-The-Fly Computation of $S_{=0}$	68
5	Future Work	79
5.1	Generalization	80
5.2	Infinite Systems	83
6	Conclusion	89

Chapter 1

Introduction

Model checking is a popular technique for automated verification of hardware- and software systems. Given a mathematical model of a system and a desired property, model checking aims at automatically verifying whether the system satisfies that property. *IC3* (shorthand for *incremental construction of inductive clauses for indubitable correctness*) is a *symbolic* model checking algorithm for reachability properties of finite transition systems: Given a finite transition system represented by means of propositional formulae (i.e., represented symbolically) and a set of target locations, IC3 decides whether these target locations are reachable in the given transition system. Its main application is the verification of sequential hardware circuits. When published by Aaron Bradley in 2011, IC3 ranked third in the UNSAT category of the hardware model checking competition (HWMCC) 2010 [Bra11, Lan19]. Later on, it was found that some rather small optimizations would have led IC3 to win that competition [EMB11]. Consequently, IC3 received a lot of attention from the model checking community. Extensions for software model checking [CG12, LNN15, Lan19] and for model checking timed pushdown systems [HB12] have been developed since.

Probabilistic Model Checking. Many systems such as randomized routing protocols exhibit probabilistic behavior. For verifying these systems, it does generally not suffice to give answers to questions like “Can the system fail?”. Consider the IPv4 zeroconf protocol as an example [BK08, Chapter 10]. In a self-configuring ad hoc network, it is necessary that new members are configured with a *unique* IP address which is not already occupied by some other member in the network. IPv4 zeroconf is a randomized protocol that aims at solving this task. When a new member M joins the network, it selects an IP address U at random. It then broadcasts a message asking whether some member M' of the network already uses address U . If M subsequently receives a response from such a member M' , then it selects a new IP address at random and repeats the procedure. If M does not receive a response after r time units, then there are two possible scenarios: Either no member in the network occupies address U or there is a member that occupies U but did not receive the broadcast message due to, e.g., message loss. Since the latter case is undesirable, M sends the broadcast message $n = 4$ times, each time waiting r time units for a response. If M did not receive a response after sending n messages, then M

Figure 1.1: A Markov chain modeling the IPv4 zeroconf protocol (taken from [BK08]).

assumes that no member in the network occupies address U .

There are two uncertainties in this scenario. First, with some positive probability q , member M selects an IP address that is already in use. Second, with some positive probability p , a broadcast message gets lost. Hence, there is always a certain probability p_{err} that M is configured with an IP address which is already in use. It is therefore not possible to establish that M will *never* be configured with a wrong IP address. Here, our goal is to establish that the probability p_{err} of M being configured with an IP address which is already in use is sufficiently small.

Suppose we are given a threshold probability λ such that we consider the IPv4 zeroconf protocol correct if $p_{\text{err}} \leq \lambda$. Establishing such an upper bound is, amongst others, the task of *probabilistic model checking*. In this thesis, we focus on *Markov chains (MCs)* as the modeling formalism for probabilistic systems. The Markov chain modeling the IPv4 zeroconf protocol is depicted in Figure 1.1. This Markov chain models the protocol in such a way that the probability of reaching error state s_6 equals p_{err} : We start in state s_0 . With probability $1 - q$, the new member M selects an IP address which is not in use. In this case, we move to state s_7 and subsequently to the success-state s_8 . Otherwise, i.e., if M selects an IP address which is in use, we move to state s_1 and start sending the broadcast messages (states s_1 – s_4). Each of these messages gets lost with probability p . If 4 subsequent messages get lost, then we reach the error-state s_6 . Otherwise, we restart the procedure and move to state s_0 . Proving the IPv4 zeroconf protocol correct boils down to proving that the probability of reaching state s_6 is at most λ .

IC3 is a very successful model checking algorithm for reachability properties of finite transition systems. Therefore, the question arises whether the fundamental concepts of IC3 can be employed for verifying or refuting such upper bounds on reachability probabilities in Markov chains. In this thesis, we investigate this question.

Contributions of this Thesis. We develop *IC3 for finite Markov chains*—an IC3-style algorithm for the quantitative variant of reachability in Markov chains:

Given a finite Markov chain \mathcal{C} , a set of goal states G , and a rational threshold λ ,
is the probability to eventually reach a state in G is at most λ ?

IC3 for Transition Systems. The first step is to identify the fundamental concepts of IC3. While existing presentations of IC3 depend on the fact that IC3 is a SAT- or SMT-based algorithm operating on symbolically represented transition systems, we develop a framework for verifying or refuting reachability properties of possibly infinite and explicitly represented transition systems via IC3. We prove the framework sound and characterize the termination behavior of its instances.

IC3 for Markov Chains. We employ our framework to develop IC3 for finite Markov chains. First, we provide a translation from the quantitative variant of reachability in Markov chains to a reachability property of an infinite transition system. After that, we develop an implementation of IC3 which is tailored to these transition systems. We prove the algorithm sound and characterize under which condition it terminates.

Given a Markov chain \mathcal{C} and a set of goal states G , IC3 for Markov chains requires the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with probability 0. Pre-computing this set can be infeasible for large or infinite Markov chains. Furthermore, such a pre-computation contradicts the incremental nature of IC3. Therefore, we extend IC3 for Markov chains by an incremental, *qualitative* reachability analysis for computing (sufficient subsets of) $S_{=0}$ on-the-fly. This extension is proven sound and we characterize the termination behavior of the extended algorithm.

Generalization. We have implemented our approach and provide experimental evaluations. These evaluations show that IC3 for *explicitly represented* Markov chains is not efficient. Therefore, in the final part of this thesis, we demonstrate that our concepts can serve as a basis for model checking *symbolically* represented Markov chains. We consider a finite Markov chain obtained from a PRISM program and show how to exploit this symbolic representation to obtain *generalizations*, which can reduce the number of required iterations drastically.

Infinite Systems. Furthermore, we discuss how our concepts can be employed for model checking (countably) *infinite* Markov chains. In particular, we consider Markov chains obtained from probabilistic pushdown automata (pPDAs) and discuss under which conditions our algorithm terminates. Furthermore, we present ideas on how to obtain generalizations for infinite Markov chains obtained from pPDAs.

Related Work. There are several works on IC3 and extensions thereof. Bradley’s seminal paper on IC3 [Bra11] is most closely related to ours since we adapt the concepts developed there. Een *et. al.* [EMB11] present an improved procedure and explain what makes IC3 effective. Hoder and Bjorner [HB12] also provide a more abstract view on IC3 (which they call *Property Directed Reachability*) by means of an abstract transition system. Furthermore, they provide a generalization of IC3 suitable for model checking

timed pushdown systems. Corollary 1 and Theorem 1 of [HB12] are similar to Theorems 3.18 and 3.20 in this thesis. However, Hoder and Bjorner focus on symbolically represented transition systems whereas we consider explicitly represented ones. Bjorner and Gurfinkel [BG15] develop another extension of IC3 for transition systems that can be encoded in the theory of Linear Real Arithmetic (LRA). They provide an algorithm to compute convex invariants. Again, their presentation is tailored to the fact that IC3 is a symbolic model checking technique and it is unclear whether and how this approach is applicable to probabilistic systems.

Seufert and Scholl [SS17] develop *reverse PDR*. Whereas Bradley’s IC3 essentially performs a backward search from the target locations in the given transition system, Seifert and Scholl develop the dual approach performing a forward search from the initial locations. This is similar to what we do in Chapter 3.4.

Cimatti and Griggio [CG12] and Lange *et. al.* [LNN15, Lan19] present procedures for model checking software via IC3. For that, they have to deal with *infinite* transition systems. In this thesis, we encounter a similar situation and adopt the approach proposed by Cimatti and Griggio to compute exact sets of predecessor locations (cf. Chapter 4).

There are several approaches for the quantitative variant of reachability in MCs. Given a finite MC \mathcal{C} , a set of goal states G , and a threshold probability λ , one approach is to compute the probability to eventually reach a state in G by means of solving a system of linear equations [BK08, Chapter 10] and comparing the result to λ . Another approach is *value iteration* [BK08, QK18], where the idea is to iteratively compute lower and upper bounds on the reachability probability. *Bounded model checking* [WBB09, BWB⁺11] is a technique where the essential idea is to enumerate paths in the Markov chain until the accumulated probability mass of these paths exceeds the threshold λ . Whereas bounded model checking can only refute that the probability to reach a state in G is at most λ , IC3 for Markov chains can refute *or* verify whether this property holds. Both approaches, value iteration and bounded model checking, are closely related to ours. IC3 for Markov chains also keeps refining upper bounds on the reachability probability by discovering ever more paths in the given Markov chain. Furthermore, in case λ equals the probability to reach a state in G , all of the three approaches value iteration, bounded model checking, and IC3 for Markov chains do not terminate in general. In contrast to that, solving a system of linear equations always terminates.

In the final part of this thesis, we consider countably infinite Markov chains obtained from probabilistic pushdown automata (pPDAs). Model checking pPDAs has been intensively studied by Esparza *et. al.* [BEKK13, KEM06]. In particular, they show that, amongst other properties, the quantitative version of reachability in pPDAs for regular sets of goal configurations is decidable. Whereas their approach is based on checking the satisfiability of a polynomial equation system, our approach operates on the countably infinite Markov chain induced by the pPDA. However, our approach is no decision procedure, i.e., it does not always halt.

Outline. Chapter 2 deals with the mathematical foundations we need in order to develop IC3 for probabilistic systems. In Chapter 3, we provide a framework for solving

reachability problems of (possibly infinite) explicitly represented transition systems via IC3. Furthermore, we consider standard IC3 for finite transition systems which is similar to the algorithm developed by Bradley.

Chapter 4 is dedicated to IC3 for finite Markov chains: In Section 4.1, we develop our algorithm. Soundness proofs and a characterization of the termination behavior of IC3 for Markov chains are provided in Section 4.2. Section 4.3 is dedicated to our implementation and experimental evaluations. In Section 4.4, we present an extension of IC3 for finite Markov chains for computing (sufficient subsets of) the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with probability 0 on-the-fly.

Finally, in Chapter 5, we discuss ideas on generalization in IC3 for Markov chains and discuss how to employ our techniques for model checking infinite Markov chains obtained from probabilistic pushdown automata.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

This chapter deals with the mathematical foundations we need in order to develop IC3 for probabilistic systems. The first section is dedicated to transition systems and the concept of defining reachable locations by means of least fixed-points of monotonic operators. The second section deals with probability theory, i.e., the mathematical foundations for modeling random experiments. Finally, in the third section, we introduce Markov chains. We study probability measures on Markov chains and how reachability probabilities are defined by means of least fixed-points of monotonic operators.

Notation. Given a set X , we denote by $2^X = \{X' \mid X' \subseteq X\}$ its power set. We denote by \mathbb{N} the set of natural numbers including 0, and by \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R} the sets of rational and real numbers, respectively. The set of rational probabilities is denoted by $[0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}} = [0, 1] \cap \mathbb{Q}$. Given two sets X and Y , we denote by

$$X^Y = \{f \mid f: Y \mapsto X\}$$

the set of all maps from Y to X .

2.1 Transition Systems

Transition systems are a straightforward model to formally describe the behavior of systems, such as software or hardware circuits. In the following, we mainly adhere to the presentation of [BK08] but adapt some definitions to our needs.

Definition 2.1 (Transition Systems). *A transition system TS is a tuple*

$$\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ}), \text{ where}$$

1. L is a non-empty, countable set of locations,
2. $I \subseteq L$ is a non-empty set of initial locations, and
3. $\text{Succ}: L \mapsto 2^L$ is a successor function.

If $l' \in \text{Succ}(l)$, we say that there is a transition from l to l' and sometimes write $l \rightarrow l'$ instead of $l' \in \text{Succ}(l)$. Furthermore, a transition system is finite iff the location space L is finite. \triangle

The intuition on transition system is as follows. The set of initial locations I determines the possible entry points of the system, i.e., at first, a location $l_0 \in I$ is chosen non-deterministically. The system then behaves according to the successor function Succ . That is, if $\text{Succ}(l_0) \neq \emptyset$, then some successor location $l_1 \in \text{Succ}(l_0)$ is chosen non-deterministically and the system “moves” to l_1 . From there, the procedure is repeated, i.e., if $\text{Succ}(l_1) \neq \emptyset$, then some $l_2 \in \text{Succ}(l_1)$ is chosen, and so on.

Example 2.2. Transition systems are conveniently represented as directed graphs where the nodes of the graph correspond to the locations of the system and the edges of the graph model the successor function. The initial locations are represented by nodes that are attached edges without a source node. Consider the transition system depicted below modeling a traffic light (adapted from [BK08]):

Formally, the above graph describes the finite transition system $\text{TS}_{\text{TL}} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$, where:

1. $L = \{R, Y, G, RY, RG, YG, RYG\}$
2. $I = \{R, G\}$
3. The successor function Succ is given by:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \text{Succ}(R) = \{RY\} & & \text{Succ}(RG) = \{RG, YG\} \\
 \text{Succ}(Y) = \{R\} & \text{Succ}(RY) = \{G\} & \text{Succ}(YG) = \{RG\} \\
 \text{Succ}(G) = \{Y\} & & \text{Succ}(RYG) = \emptyset
 \end{array}$$

For every possible combination of simultaneously activated lights red (R), yellow (Y), and green (G), there is a corresponding location. As described by the set of initial locations I , the traffic light starts with only the red light (R) or only the green light (G) being activated. After showing the red light, it shows red and yellow (RY). From there, it continues with showing the green light (G). Finally, after the green light, it shows the yellow light (Y) and starts with red (R) again. For test purposes, engineers also implemented the behavior of the traffic light when showing red and green (RG) or yellow and green (YG). When showing (RG), the traffic light either idles in that location, i.e., it moves to (RG) again, or it switches to (YG). From there, the system can move to (RG) again. In location (RYG) no further action is possible as $\text{Succ}(RYG) = \emptyset$. \triangle

Reachability Properties. Now that we modeled the behavior of the traffic light by means of the transition system TS_{TL} , we can make use of it to determine whether the traffic light obeys certain properties of interest. In this thesis, the focus lies on *reachability properties*: Given a transition system $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ and a set of target locations $\text{Target} \subseteq L$, is some location $l \in \text{Target}$ reachable? For the traffic light considered in Example 2.2, for instance, the following is a reachability property:

“It will never happen that the red and the green light are activated simultaneously, i.e., location (RG) is unreachable.”

Determining whether a given transition system satisfies a given reachability property thus amounts to determining whether a given set of locations is reachable. Therefore, we now introduce the notion of reachability in transition systems.

Reachability in Transition Systems. In what follows, we take two views on reachability: An operational view that defines reachable locations and sets of locations, respectively, by means of paths through the transition system, and a denotational view that defines reachability by means of a monotonic operator on sets of locations. The latter is important for understanding the fundamental concepts underlying IC3 while the former is more suitable for our intuitive understanding. We start with the operational view.

Definition 2.3 (Paths). Let $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ be a transition system. A (finite) path of length n is a sequence of locations $\pi = l_0 l_1 \dots l_n$ with $l_{i-1} \rightarrow l_i$ for all $1 \leq i < n$. We denote by $\pi[i]$ the i -th location of path π , i.e. $\pi[i] = l_i$. A path π is called initial iff it starts in an initial location, i.e., $\pi[0] \in I$. We denote by $\text{Paths}(\text{TS})$ the set of all initial paths of transition system TS . \triangle

Intuitively, a path of a TS describes one possible behavior of the described system. Reconsider TS_{TL} from Example 2.2. One possible behavior is (R)(RY)(G), i.e., showing red, then red and yellow, and finally green. An impossible behavior is, e.g., (R)(RY)(RG), since there is no transition from (RY) to (RG). The set $\text{Paths}(\text{TS})$ can thus be seen as the set of all possible behaviors of TS. Paths give rise to the notion of reachability.

Definition 2.4 (Reachable locations—operational view). Let $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ be a transition system. A location $l \in L$ is reachable in at most $k \in \mathbb{N}$ steps iff there is an initial path $\pi \in \text{Paths}(\text{TS})$ of length at most k with $\pi[i] = l$ for some i . Otherwise, l is called unreachable in at most k steps. A location $l \in L$ is reachable iff there is an initial path $\pi \in \text{Paths}(\text{TS})$ with $\pi[i] = l$ for some i . Otherwise, we say that l is unreachable. A set of locations $X \subseteq L$ is called reachable iff some $l \in X$ is reachable. Otherwise, X is called unreachable. \triangle

Reconsider Example 2.2. Both location (R) and location (G) are reachable in (at most) 0 steps. Locations (Y) and (RY) are reachable in at most 1 step, and location (RG) is unreachable.

Next, we take the *denotational* view on reachability, i.e., we define reachable locations by means of a monotonic operator. For that, consider the following definition.

Definition 2.5 (Reachability Operator). Given a transition system $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$, the induced reachability operator Φ is a map defined as

$$\Phi: 2^L \mapsto 2^L, \quad \Phi(X) = I \cup \bigcup_{l \in X} \text{Succ}(l). \quad \triangle$$

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the fixed-point iterations.

Given a set of locations X , we denote by $\Phi^k(X)$ the k -fold application of Φ to the argument, i.e., $\Phi^0(X) = X$ and $\Phi^{k+1}(X) = \Phi(\Phi^k(X))$. The reachability operator defines the reachable locations of a given TS in a step-wise fashion: The locations reachable in at most 0 are given by $\Phi^1(\emptyset) = I$, i.e., the set of initial locations. The locations reachable in at most 1 step are given by $\Phi^2(\emptyset) = I \cup \bigcup_{l \in I} \text{Succ}(l)$, i.e., all initial locations plus all the locations reachable from an initial location in one step. The same intuition holds for $\Phi^3(\emptyset)$, $\Phi^4(\emptyset)$, and so on. We often write $\Phi^i(I)$ instead of $\Phi^{i+1}(\emptyset)$ for the set of locations reachable in at most i steps for the sake of convenience. The set of *all* reachable locations is obtained by taking the supremum over all step bounds. We formalize this in the following definition, which is equivalent to Definition 2.4.

Definition 2.6 (Reachable locations—denotational view). *Let $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ be a transition system. The set $\text{Reach}^{\leq i}$ of locations reachable in at most $i \in \mathbb{N}$ steps and the set Reach of reachable locations are defined as*

$$\text{Reach}^{\leq i} = \Phi^i(I) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Reach} = \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\emptyset) = \text{lfp } X. \Phi(X).$$

A set of locations $X \subseteq S$ is called reachable in at most k steps iff $X \cap \text{Reach}^{\leq k} \neq \emptyset$. Otherwise, X is called unreachable in at most k steps. Moreover, X is called reachable iff $X \cap \text{Reach} \neq \emptyset$. Otherwise, X is called unreachable. \triangle

The fact that the above supremum coincides with the least fixed-point of Φ follows from the Kleene fixed-point theorem [LNS82]: Since Φ is a continuous operator (cf. Lemma 2.8) over the complete lattice $(2^L, \subseteq)$, it has a least fixed point, which is obtained from taking the supremum of the fixed-point iterations starting from the bottom element \emptyset of the lattice. For finite transition systems, this fixed-point is always reached after finitely many fixed-point iterations. For infinite systems, however, this is not the case in general.

Example 2.7. *Figure 2.1 demonstrates the effect of the fixed-point iterations. Each iteration reveals locations reachable in one more step. Further, notice why it is necessary to define Reach*

as the least fixed-point of Φ : Another fixed-point of Φ is given by the whole location space L , since $\Phi(L) = L$. In the given TS, however, it is obvious that L contains locations that are unreachable, namely l_6 , l_7 , and l_8 . Consequently, only the least fixed-point precisely captures the set of reachable locations. \triangle

Finally, we will make use of the fact that Φ is continuous and hence monotonic.

Lemma 2.8. *For every transition system $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$, the induced reachability operator Φ is continuous, i.e., for all $\mathcal{A} \subseteq 2^L$ it holds that*

$$\Phi\left(\bigcup \mathcal{A}\right) = \bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{A}} \Phi(X).$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi\left(\bigcup \mathcal{A}\right) \\ &= I \cup \bigcup_{l \in \bigcup \mathcal{A}} \text{Succ}(l) && \text{(Def. of } \Phi) \\ &= I \cup \bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{A}} \bigcup_{l \in X} \text{Succ}(l) \\ &= \bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{A}} \left(I \cup \bigcup_{l \in X} \text{Succ}(l) \right) \\ &= \bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{A}} \Phi(X). && \text{(Def. of } \Phi) \end{aligned}$$

\square

2.2 Probability Theory

In this section, we introduce the basics of discrete probability theory we need in order to define probability measures on Markov chains. We adhere to the presentation of [Kle14].

In order to model random experiments mathematically, we first fix a *sample space* Ω . This set is assumed to contain all possible outcomes of the experiment. For this reason, elements $\omega \in \Omega$ are often referred to as *samples* or *outcomes*. A subset of Ω is called *event*. Given an event A , we denote by \bar{A} its complement, i.e., $\bar{A} = \Omega \setminus A$. A σ -algebra Σ over Ω determines for which events A it makes sense to speak about its probability measure.

Definition 2.9 (σ -algebra, Measurable Space). *Let Ω be a non-empty, countable set. A σ -algebra over Ω is a set $\Sigma \subseteq 2^\Omega$ satisfying:*

1. Ω is an element of Σ , i.e., $\Omega \in \Sigma$.
2. Σ is closed under complements, i.e., if $A \in \Sigma$, then $\Omega \setminus A \in \Sigma$.
3. Σ is closed under countable unions, i.e., if $A_1, A_2, \dots \in \Sigma$, then $\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \in \Sigma$.

The pair (Ω, Σ) is called *measurable space*. \triangle

Events $A \in \Sigma$ are called *measurable*. A measurable space allows us to define a *probability measure* on it, which assigns a probability to each measurable event $A \in \Sigma$.

Definition 2.10 (Probability Measure, Probability Space). *Let (Ω, Σ) be a measurable space. A probability measure on (Ω, Σ) is a map $\Pr: \Sigma \mapsto [0, 1]$ such that:*

1. \Pr assigns probability 1 to event Ω , i.e., $\Pr(\Omega) = 1$.
2. Given pair-wise disjoint measurable events $A_1, A_2, \dots \in \Sigma$, the probability of the event $\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i$ is the sum of the probabilities of A_1, A_2, \dots , i.e.,

$$\Pr\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \Pr(A_i).$$

The triple (Ω, Σ, \Pr) is called a probability space. △

If $A = \{\omega\} \subseteq \Sigma$ is a singleton, we often write $\Pr(\omega)$ instead of $\Pr(\{\omega\})$. Summing up, a σ -algebra Σ over Ω determines for which events A it makes sense to speak about its *probability* $\Pr(A)$. Hence, a probability space (Ω, Σ, \Pr) defines the possible outcomes, which events are measurable, and a probability measure on these events.

Example 2.11. *We model throwing a fair, six-sided die by means of a probability space (Ω, Σ, \Pr) . The components are defined as follows:*

1. *After throwing a six-sided die, we either get 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, or 6. Hence, our sample space Ω is given by*

$$\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}.$$

2. *It is easy to verify that a σ -algebra Σ over Ω is given by $\Sigma = 2^{\Omega}$.*

3. \Pr is the unique probability measure on (Ω, Σ) satisfying

$$\Pr(i) = 1/6 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, 6\}.$$

The described probability space now allows to ask for the probability of certain events. The probability of the event $\{3\}$ that after throwing the die we see a 3 is trivially given by $\Pr(\{3\}) = 1/6$. The probability of the event $\{2, 3\}$, i.e., whether we see 2 or 3, is, according to Definition 2.10 (2), equal to the sum of the probabilities of $\{2\}$ and $\{3\}$, i.e.,

$$\Pr(\{2, 3\}) = \Pr(\{2\}) + \Pr(\{3\}) = 1/6 + 1/6 = 1/3.$$

An important property of probability measures is the fact that for the complement \bar{A} of $A \in \Sigma$ it holds that $\Pr(\bar{A}) = 1 - \Pr(A)$. Using this, we obtain that the probability of getting no outcome is 0 since $\Pr(\emptyset) = 1 - \Pr(\Omega) = 0$. △

2.3 Markov Chains

Transition systems are suitable for specifying the behavior of systems that behave non-deterministically since a location may have multiple successor locations. Each transition from a location to a successor of this location models the possibility that the system behaves in that way. This enables giving an answer to invariant properties like “Under all possible behaviors, is it possible that the traffic light will show the red and the green light simultaneously?” (cf. Example 2.2). However, all we know is whether a certain behavior is possible or not. It is *not* possible to answer questions like “Is the probability that the system behaves badly at most 0.01?”. In order to give an answer to those questions, probabilistic models come into play. In this section, we study Markov chains. Here we mainly adhere to the presentation of [BK08], which we also refer to for further reading on probabilistic model checking.

The intuitive understanding of a Markov chain is similar to that of a transition system except for the fact that, in a Markov chain, it is quantified *how likely* it is to move from a given location to another. To avoid confusion in the following chapters, locations of a Markov chain are called *states*.

Definition 2.12 ((Discrete-Time) Markov Chains). *A Markov chain (or MC) \mathcal{C} is a triple*

$$\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P), \text{ where}$$

1. S is a non-empty, countable set of states,
2. s_I is an initial state, and
3. $P: S \times S \mapsto [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$ is a transition probability function satisfying

$$\sum_{s' \in S} P(s, s') = 1 \quad \text{for all } s \in S.$$

\mathcal{C} is called *finite* iff the underlying state space S is finite. If $P(s, s') > 0$, then we say that state s' is a (direct) successor of state s . △

Notice that we restrict the codomain of P to *rational* probabilities. As we did for transition system, we first give an intuition on what a Markov chain is supposed to model. An MC \mathcal{C} has a single initial state s_I where the system is assumed to start. In contrast to transition systems, we now *sample* a successor according to the transition probability function P . That is, state s is chosen with probability $P(s_I, s)$ (read: the probability to move from s_I to s) for all $s \in S$. From that state s , the procedure is repeated, i.e., state s' is chosen with probability $P(s, s')$ and so on. Notice that for all $s \in S$, there is at least one state s' with $P(s, s') > 0$, i.e., every state has at least one successor.

Example 2.13. *We represent Markov chains as directed graphs with probabilities attached to the transitions. The initial state has an incoming edge without source node. Formally, the graph in Figure 2.2 describes the following Markov chain $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$:*

1. The state space is given by $S = \{s_I, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4\}$.

Figure 2.2: A sample Markov chain.

2. The initial state s_I has an incoming edge without source.
3. The transition probability function is defined as

$$P(s, s') = p \quad \text{iff} \quad \text{there is an edge from } s \text{ to } s' \text{ labeled with } p$$

for all $s, s' \in S$.

△

Reachability Probabilities in Markov Chains. In order to define reachability probabilities in Markov chains, we define the set of (infinite) paths of a given MC.

Definition 2.14. Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC. An (infinite) path π of \mathcal{C} is an infinite sequence of states, i.e., $\pi = s_0 s_1 s_2 \dots$ with $P(s_i, s_{i+1}) > 0$ for all $i \geq 0$. We denote by $\text{Paths}(\mathcal{C})$ the set of all infinite paths of \mathcal{C} starting in s_I . By $\text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C})$ we denote the set of all finite paths starting in s_I , i.e., the set of all paths $\hat{\pi} = s_0 \dots s_n$ with $s_0 = s_I$ and $P(s_i, s_{i+1}) > 0$ for all $0 \leq i < n$. △

For the MC \mathcal{C} depicted in Figure 2.2, we have $s_I s_2 s_1 (s_I s_1)^\omega \in \text{Paths}(\mathcal{C})$, where $(s_I s_1)^\omega$ denotes the infinite sequence $s_I s_1 s_I s_1 s_I s_1 \dots$. Towards defining a probability measure on sets of infinite paths, we define cylinder sets:

Definition 2.15 (Cylinder Sets). Let \mathcal{C} be an MC. The cylinder set of a finite path $\hat{\pi} = s_I \dots s_n \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C})$ is defined as

$$\text{Cyl}(\hat{\pi}) = \{\pi \in \text{Paths}(\mathcal{C}) \mid \hat{\pi} \in \text{pref}(\pi)\},$$

where $\text{pref}(\pi)$ is the set of all finite prefixes of π . △

A set X of infinite paths is thus characterized by a finite path fragment all paths in X have in common. Cylinder sets give rise to a probability space associated with an MC.

Definition 2.16 (Probability Space of a Markov Chain). Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC. We associate the following measurable space (Ω, Σ) :

1. The set of outcomes Ω is the set of all paths, i.e., $\Omega = \text{Paths}(\mathcal{C})$.
2. Σ is the smallest σ -algebra that contains all cylinder sets $\text{Cyl}(\hat{\pi})$ for all $\hat{\pi} \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C})$.

The probability measure $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}$ is given by

$$\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\text{Cyl}(s_0 \dots s_n)) = P(s_0 \dots s_n),$$

where the probability $P(s_0 \dots s_n)$ of a finite path $s_0 \dots s_n$ is defined as

$$P(s_0 \dots s_n) = \prod_{0 \leq i < n} P(s_i, s_{i+1}).$$

For finite paths consisting of a single state s_0 , we define $P(s_0) = 1$. △

The probability of a set of infinite paths $\text{Cyl}(\hat{\pi})$ for some finite path $\hat{\pi} \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C})$ is determined by multiplying the probabilities along $\hat{\pi}$. For the MC \mathcal{C} given in Example 2.13, one cylinder set is given by $\text{Cyl}(s_I s_2 s_1 s_I)$. The corresponding probability is given by

$$\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\text{Cyl}(\hat{\pi})) = P(s_I s_2 s_1 s_I) = 2/3 \cdot 1/3 \cdot 1/2 = 1/9.$$

With the presented prerequisites at hand, we are now in a position to define reachability probabilities in Markov chains. More precisely, we define the following: Given an MC $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ and a set of goal states $G \subseteq S$, what is the probability of eventually reaching a state in G ? Hence, we are interested in characterizing the probability of $\diamond G = \{\pi \in \text{Paths}(\mathcal{C}) \mid \pi[i] \in G \text{ for some } i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ —the set of all paths that eventually visit a state in G . Event $\diamond G$ is measurable and its probability is expressed as follows: Let $(S \setminus G)^* G \subseteq \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C})$ denote the set of all finite paths $\hat{\pi} = s_0 \dots s_{n-1} s_n$ with $s_0, \dots, s_{n-1} \notin G$ and $s_n \in G$. The probability $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G)$ is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) &= \sum_{s_0 \dots s_n \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C}) \cap (S \setminus G)^* G} \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\text{Cyl}(s_0 \dots s_n)) \\ &= \sum_{s_0 \dots s_n \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C}) \cap (S \setminus G)^* G} P(s_0 \dots s_n). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the probability of eventually reaching a state in G is given by the sum of the probabilities of all finite paths that start in s_I and end in a state in G . Using this definition to actually determine the probability of $\diamond G$ can be intricate as there might be infinitely many of such paths. This also holds for the MC depicted in Example 2.13: To determine $\diamond\{s_4\}$, i.e., the probability to eventually reach the goal state s_4 , we have to consider infinitely many finite paths from s_I to s_4 . For finite MCs, reachability probabilities can be computed in polynomial time by solving a linear equation system [BK08].

For developing IC3 for probabilistic systems, it is more convenient to define reachability probabilities by means of the least fixed-point of a monotonic operator—similar to what we have seen for transition systems.

Given $v \in [0, 1]^S$, we often write $v[s]$ instead of $v(s)$ for the sake of readability. The aforementioned operator is defined as follows:

Definition 2.17 (Reachability Probability Operator). Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC and let $G \subseteq S$. The reachability operator w.r.t. \mathcal{C} and G is defined as

$$\Upsilon: [0, 1]^S \mapsto [0, 1]^S, \quad \Upsilon(v)[s] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in G \\ \sum_{s' \in S} P(s, s') \cdot v[s'], & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \triangle$$

Both the MC \mathcal{C} and the set G will always be clear from the context. The reachability probability operator defines reachability probabilities in a step-wise fashion: We start with the 0-step reachability probabilities. For $s \in G$, the probability to reach a state in G from state s in 0 steps is 1, since we are in G already. For all other states, this probability is 0. Hence, the map $v_0 \in [0, 1]^S$ that assigns to each $s \in S$ the probability $v_0[s]$ to reach a state in G in 0 steps is given by

$$v_0[s] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in G \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The map v_1 that assigns to each $s \in S$ the probability $v_1[s]$ to reach a state in G in at most 1 step is determined by the reachability probability operator as follows: For $s \in S \setminus G$, the probability to reach a state in G in at most 1 step is given by the sum of the probabilities to reach a state in G in 0 steps via successors s' of s , each summand being weighted according to the probability to move from s to s' . Reconsider the MC \mathcal{C} from Example 2.13. The probability to reach s_4 from s_2 in at most 1 step is given by

$$1/3 \cdot v_0[s_1] + 1/3 \cdot v_0[s_3] + 1/3 \cdot v_0[s_4] = 1/3 \cdot 0 + 1/3 \cdot 0 + 1/3 \cdot 1 = 1/3.$$

For states $s \in G$, the probability to reach a state in G simply remains 1. In a nutshell, the 1-step reachability probabilities are given by $\Upsilon(v_0)$. The same intuition holds for the 2-step reachability probabilities $v_2 = \Upsilon(v_1)$, the 3-step reachability probabilities $v_3 = \Upsilon(v_2)$, and so on. In general, the k -step reachability probabilities v_k , i.e., the map that assigns to each state s the probability to reach a state in G from state s in at most k steps, is given by $v_k = \Upsilon^k(v_0)$. The probability to eventually reach a state in G from state s (in arbitrary many steps) is then given by the supremum of the k -step reachability probabilities for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, which coincides with the least fixed-point of Υ .

Definition 2.18 (Reachability Probabilities). Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC and let $G \subseteq S$. The probability $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G)$ to reach a state in G from state s in at most $k \in \mathbb{N}$ steps is given by

$$\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G) = \Upsilon^k(v_0)[s].$$

Furthermore, the probability $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G)$ to eventually reach a state in G from state s is given by

$$\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G) = \left(\sup_k \Upsilon^k(v_0) \right)[s] = (\text{lfp } v. \Upsilon(v))[s].$$

In particular, we have $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = \Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond G)$. \triangle

In general, the reachability probability operator Υ has several fixed-points. For many applications such as, e.g., computing $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G)$ for a finite MC \mathcal{C} , it is important to restrict

that operator in such a way that it has a *unique* least fixed-point. For that, fix an MC $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ and a set of goal states G . We define the set

$$S_{>0} = \left\{ s \in S \mid \Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G) > 0 \right\}$$

of states s that eventually reach some state in G with a strictly positive probability. Furthermore, we define $S_{=0} = S \setminus S_{>0}$. If \mathcal{C} is finite, then $S_{>0}$ can be computed by means of a graph analysis: Consider the directed graph obtained from \mathcal{C} by omitting the transition probabilities. We then have $s \in S_{>0}$ iff there is a (directed) path from s to a state in G for all $s \in S_{>0}$. The *restricted* reachability probability operator is defined as follows:

Definition 2.19 (Restricted Reachability Probability Operator). *Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC and let $G \subseteq S$. The restricted reachability probability operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$ is defined as*

$$\Upsilon_{>0}: [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mapsto [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}, \quad \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in G \\ \sum_{s' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}} P(s, s') \cdot v[s'], & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \triangle$$

Operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$ has a *unique* least fixed-point for every *finite* MC \mathcal{C} and all $G \subseteq S$. Let $v_0 \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ denote the map from states to probabilities from above restricted to states in $S_{>0}$. If $s \notin S_{>0}$, then $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G) = 0$. Otherwise, i.e., if $s \in S_{>0}$, then $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G) = \Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)$ and $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G) = (\text{lfp } v. \Upsilon_{>0}(v))[s]$. If \mathcal{C} is finite, then the reachability probabilities $v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $v[s] = \Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G)$ for all $s \in S_{>0}$ are given by the unique solution of the linear equation system

$$v[s] = \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s] \quad \text{for all } s \in S_{>0}.$$

Example 2.20. *Reconsider the MC \mathcal{C} from Figure 2.2. We determine the probability $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G)$ of eventually reaching $G = \{s_4\}$. For that, we compute $S_{>0} = \{s_I, s_1, s_2, s_4\}$. Notice that $s_3 \notin S_{>0}$ as there is no path from s_3 to s_4 . We thus obtain the following linear equation system:*

$$\begin{aligned} v[s_I] &= 1/3 \cdot v[s_1] + 2/3 \cdot v[s_2] & v[s_1] &= 1/2 \cdot v[s_4] + 1/2 \cdot v[s_I] \\ v[s_2] &= 1/3 \cdot v[s_4] + 1/3 \cdot v[s_1] & v[s_4] &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

Solving the system yields $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = v[s_I] = 9/13$.

\triangle

Chapter 3

IC3 for Transition Systems

Towards our goal of developing IC3 for probabilistic systems, we study IC3 for solving reachability problems (i.e., verifying or refuting reachability properties) of possibly infinite transition systems. For that, we formally define reachability problems in the first section. In particular, we study inductive strengthenings—a notion which is central to IC3. In the second section, we present a framework for solving reachability problems of transition systems via IC3. That is, we present a parameterized algorithm, explain the general concept IC3 employs to solve reachability problems, and provide formal specifications of its ingredients. The third and the fourth section are dedicated to concrete implementations of IC3 for reachability problems of *finite* transition systems. Finally, in the fifth section, we prove our IC3 framework sound and provide theorems characterizing the termination behavior of its instances.

3.1 Reachability Problems

A reachability problem consists of a transition system $TS = (L, I, Succ)$ and a set of locations $Target$ whose reachability is to be determined.

Definition 3.1 (Reachability Problem). *A reachability problem is a tuple*

$$\mathcal{R} = (TS, Target), \text{ where}$$

1. $TS = (L, I, Succ)$ is a transition system, and
2. $Target \subseteq L$ is a set of target locations.

Furthermore, we define $coTarget = L \setminus Target$. △

From now on, we implicitly assume that for a given reachability problem \mathcal{R} , the components are denoted as in the definition above, i.e., $\mathcal{R} = (TS, Target)$ with $TS = (L, I, Succ)$. Furthermore, by Φ we always denote the reachability operator induced by TS .

Example 3.2. *Figure 3.1 depicts an example of a reachability problem. Locations belonging to $Target$ are depicted in red. Dually, locations belonging to $coTarget$ are depicted in green. In this example, $Target$ is unreachable.* △

Figure 3.1: A reachability problem $\mathcal{R} = (\text{TS}, \text{Target})$ with $\text{Target} = \{s_8\}$.

For every such reachability problem $\mathcal{R} = (\text{TS}, \text{Target})$, it either holds that Target is reachable or that Target is unreachable. Solving \mathcal{R} means to determine which of these cases hold. Additionally, we provide a certificate that allows to verify that the given answer is indeed correct. We consider these cases separately.

Case 1: Target is reachable. According to Definition 2.6, if Target is reachable, then there is a location $l \in \text{Target}$ such that l is reachable, i.e., $l \in \text{Reach} = \text{lfp } X. \Phi(X)$. Furthermore, the fact that the reachability operator Φ is continuous implies that l is reachable within *finitely* many steps.

Lemma 3.3. *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem and assume that Target is reachable. Then Target is reachable within finitely many steps, i.e., there is a $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\text{Reach}^{\leq k} \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. By contradiction. Recall that $\text{Reach}^{\leq k} = \Phi^{k+1}(\emptyset)$. Now suppose there is no $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the above property holds, i.e., suppose for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ it holds that

$$\Phi^k(\emptyset) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset.$$

Since $\text{coTarget} = L \setminus \text{Target}$, it follows that $\Phi^k(\emptyset) \subseteq \text{coTarget}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Now, due to the fact that coTarget is an upper bound on $\Phi^k(\emptyset)$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we get

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\emptyset) \subseteq \text{coTarget}.$$

Since the above supremum coincides with the least fixed-point of Φ , we get

$$\text{lfp } X. \Phi(X) \subseteq \text{coTarget}.$$

Hence, we have $\text{Reach} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$, which is a contradiction. \square

Consequently, in case Target is reachable, we can always provide a natural number k such that some $l \in \text{Target}$ is reachable within k steps. This natural number k serves as our certificate for the reachability of Target .

Figure 3.2: The reachability problem from Figure 3.1. The blue locations depict an inductive strengthening of coTarget.

Case 2: Target is unreachable. In order to determine and to witness that Target is unreachable, we employ the principle of induction. Consider the transition system depicted in Figure 3.1 on page 20 as a running example. Clearly, $\text{Target} = \{l_8\}$ is unreachable. In order to prove that Target is unreachable, we show that *at most* the locations in coTarget (depicted in green) are reachable. Let us try to prove that by induction. For that, we have to show that the following two conditions adapted from [Bra11] hold:

1. Initiation: coTarget contains the initial locations, i.e., $I \subseteq \text{coTarget}$.
2. Consecution: All successors of locations in coTarget are in coTarget, i.e.,

$$\forall l \in \text{coTarget}: \text{Succ}(l) \subseteq \text{coTarget} .$$

In terms of proofs by induction, the proposition “at most the locations in coTarget are reachable” is *both* our proof obligation and our induction hypothesis. For the example shown in Figure 3.1, initiation is fulfilled. Consecution, however, fails: We have $l_7 \in \text{coTarget}$ and $\text{Succ}(l_7) = \{l_8\} \not\subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Hence, coTarget is too weak to serve as an induction hypothesis in order to prove that no more locations than those in coTarget are reachable. That is, we have to find a subset $\text{Inv} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$ that fulfills both initiation and consecution. We call Inv an *inductive strengthening of coTarget*.

Definition 3.4 (Inductive Strengthening (adapted from [Bra11])). *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem. An inductive strengthening (of coTarget) is a set of locations $\text{Inv} \subseteq L$ satisfying:*

1. All locations in Inv are in coTarget, i.e., $\text{Inv} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$.
2. Inv satisfies both initiation and consecution, i.e., $\Phi(\text{Inv}) \subseteq \text{Inv}$. △

An inductive strengthening Inv of coTarget is a certificate for the unreachability of Target : Initiation and consecution imply that at most locations in Inv are reachable. Since $\text{Inv} \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, this implies that Target is unreachable.

Lemma 3.5. *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem and let Inv be an inductive strengthening of coTarget . Then Target is unreachable, i.e., $\text{Reach} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$.*

Proof. We employ Park's Lemma [Par69], which states that for every continuous self-map over a complete lattice like the reachability operator Φ it holds that

$$\Phi(\text{Inv}) \subseteq \text{Inv} \quad \text{implies} \quad \text{lfp } X. \Phi(X) \subseteq \text{Inv} .$$

By definition of inductive strengthenings, we further have $\text{Inv} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. We thus get

$$\text{Reach} = \text{lfp } X. \Phi(X) \subseteq \text{coTarget} ,$$

which completes the proof. \square

For our running example, an inductive strengthening Inv is depicted in Figure 3.2. Inv contains all initial locations and for all locations $l \in \text{Inv}$ it holds that all successors $l' \in \text{Succ}(l)$ are elements of Inv again. Notice that an inductive strengthening Inv of coTarget might contain unreachable locations such as l_9 and l_{10} . If Target is unreachable, then there is at least one inductive strengthening given by the set of reachable locations.

Lemma 3.6. *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem and assume that Target is unreachable. Then there is an inductive strengthening Inv given by $\text{Inv} = \text{Reach}$.*

Proof. Recall that $\text{Reach} = \text{lfp } X. \Phi(X)$. Since Target is unreachable, we have $\text{Reach} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Furthermore, Reach is a fixed-point of Φ and hence $\Phi(\text{Reach}) = \text{Reach} \subseteq \text{Reach}$. Consequently, Reach satisfies the conditions of an inductive strengthening of coTarget . \square

Reconsider Figure 3.2. Clearly, another inductive strengthening of coTarget is given by $\text{Reach} = \{l_0, \dots, l_5\}$. Consequently, inductive strengthenings are not necessarily unique.

3.2 Algorithm and Specifications

We now present IC3 for reachability problems of transition systems adapted from [Bra11]. The presentation in [Bra11, Bra12] as well as literature on extensions of IC3 [EMB11, HB12, BG15, SS17], mostly deal with *symbolically* represented transition systems. That is, locations and the successor function are represented by formulae over certain theories. Moreover, the presented algorithms directly employ SAT- or SMT queries on these symbolic representations. Since this is rather unsuitable for developing IC3 for probabilistic systems, we now present a framework for solving reachability problems of *explicitly represented* transition systems via IC3.

Algorithm 1 shown in Figure 3.3 is called $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$. It is parameterized by a class of reachability problems \mathfrak{A} and by procedure Strengthen. Different classes of reachability problems might require different implementations of procedure Strengthen. The implementation of Strengthen for finite transition systems provided by Bradley [Bra11], for instance, is not applicable for the class of reachability problems that arises from finite Markov chains as we will see in Chapter 4. Proceeding in this more general fashion allows us to specify IC3 and procedure Strengthen independent of which particular class of reachability problems we consider. Algorithm 1 can thus be seen as a framework for solving reachability problems of transition systems via IC3. In what follows, we explain the general concept $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ employs to solve reachability problems $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$ for an arbitrary class of reachability problems \mathfrak{A} . A concrete implementation of IC3 for reachability problems of *finite* transition systems is provided in the subsequent section.

The goal of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is to solve reachability problems $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. We thus specify it as follows:

Definition 3.7 (Specification of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems. We say that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is sound iff the following partial correctness properties hold for all inputs $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$:*

1. *If Target is unreachable and the call $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ terminates, then it returns **unreachable**.*
2. *If Target is reachable and the call $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ terminates, then it returns **reachable**.*

Moreover, we say that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is complete iff $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ terminates for all $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. \triangle

The distinction between soundness and completeness is important because if the underlying location space L of reachability problems $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$ is infinite, then termination of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ cannot be guaranteed in general. Now fix a reachability problem $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. Before we go into the details of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$, we consider the general concept IC3 employs to solve \mathcal{R} . The idea is to proceed incrementally: For increasing $k = 0, 1, \dots$, the algorithm computes sets of locations $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$ called *frames*, which are steadily refined during the computation. Every frame F_i overapproximates the locations reachable in at most i steps. If Target is reachable, then $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ eventually finds a natural number k such that Target is reachable in k steps and subsequently terminates returning **unreachable**. Otherwise, i.e., if Target is unreachable, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ continues extending and refining the frames until it eventually finds an inductive strengthening of coTarget among these frames, or does not terminate. Central to $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is that it maintains the *IC3-Invariants*, which consist of four conditions the frames F_0, \dots, F_k must obey.

Definition 3.8 (IC3-Invariants). *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem and let $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The following conditions are called IC3-Invariants for the frames $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$:*

1. *Initiality: $F_0 = I$*
2. *Chain-Property: $\forall 0 \leq i < k: F_i \subseteq F_{i+1}$*
3. *Frame-Safety: $\forall 0 \leq i \leq k: F_i \subseteq \text{coTarget}$*
4. *Relative Inductiveness: $\forall 0 \leq i < k: \Phi(F_i) \subseteq F_{i+1}$*

We say that F_0, \dots, F_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants iff the above conditions hold. Finally, if $\Phi(F_i) \subseteq F_{i+1}$, we say that F_{i+1} is inductive relative to F_i . \triangle

Algorithm 1: IC3 $[\mathfrak{A}]$ (\mathcal{R})

Data: A reachability problem $\mathcal{R} = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{A}$.
Result: According to Definition 3.7.

```

1 if  $I \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$  or  $\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$  then
2   | return reachable;
3  $F_0 \leftarrow I$ ;
4  $F_1 \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
5  $k \leftarrow 1$ ;
6 while True do
7   | (flag,  $F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
8   |   Strengthen $[\mathfrak{A}]$ ( $\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k$ );
9   | if flag then
10  |   | return reachable;
11  |    $F_0, \dots, F_k \leftarrow F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ ;
12  |    $F_{k+1} \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
13  |    $k \leftarrow k + 1$ ;
14  |   if  $\exists 0 \leq i < k: F_i = F_{i+1}$  then
15  |   | return unreachable;
16 end

```

Figure 3.3: IC3 for solving reachability problems $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. Variables $F_0, F_1, \dots \subseteq L$ are called *frames*. The loop beginning in Line 6 is called *main loop* and its iterations are called *main iterations*.

Fix some frames $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$. Initiality ensures that F_0 is the set of initial locations. The chain-property requires that the frames form a chain w.r.t. \subseteq . Frame-safety says that *no* frame must ever contain a location $l \in \text{Target}$. Relative inductiveness deserves special attention. Due to initiality and the chain-property, we have $I \subseteq F_i$ for all $0 \leq i \leq k$. Relative inductiveness can thus be rephrased as

$$\forall l \in F_i: \text{Succ}(l) \subseteq F_{i+1} \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq i < k .$$

In words, frame F_{i+1} must cover all successors of locations in F_i . This is illustrated by Figure 3.4. Consequently, initiality and relative inductiveness imply that frame F_i indeed overapproximates the set of locations reachable in at most i steps: For $i = 0$, this is ensured by initiality. The case $i > 0$ follows by relative inductiveness.

Lemma 3.9. *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem, let $k \geq 1$ be a natural number, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$ be frames satisfying the IC3-Invariants. Then frame F_i overapproximates the set $\text{Reach}^{\leq i}$ of locations reachable in at most i steps. Formally: $\forall 0 \leq i \leq k: \text{Reach}^{\leq i} \subseteq F_i$*

Proof. By induction on k . Recall that $\text{Reach}^{\leq i} = \Phi^i(I)$.

Base case. Initiality implies $F_0 = I = \Phi^0(I)$. Furthermore, relative inductiveness yields $\Phi(F_0) \subseteq F_1$. Together, this yields $\Phi(F_0) = \Phi^1(I) \subseteq F_1$.

Figure 3.4: Illustration of frames F_0, \dots, F_3 satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

Induction hypothesis. Assume for an arbitrary but fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \geq 1$ that

$$\Phi^i(I) \subseteq F_i \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq i \leq k.$$

Induction step. We have to show that $\Phi^{k+1}(I) \subseteq F_{k+1}$. Since $\Phi^k(I) \subseteq F_k$ by I.H., monotonicity of Φ (cf. Lemma 2.8) yields $\Phi^{k+1}(I) = \Phi(\Phi^k(I)) \subseteq \Phi(F_k)$. Now, Relative Inductiveness, i.e., $\Phi(F_k) \subseteq F_{k+1}$, and transitivity of \subseteq imply

$$\Phi^{k+1}(I) \subseteq F_{k+1}.$$

This completes the proof. \square

The IC3-Invariants also yield the termination criterion of IC3[[\mathcal{A}]] in case Target is unreachable: If, in the course of the computation, eventually two consecutive frames collapse, i.e., $F_i = F_{i+1}$ for some $0 \leq i < k$, then frame F_i is an inductive strengthening of coTarget. Lemma 3.5 then implies that Target is unreachable.

Lemma 3.10. *Let \mathcal{R} be a reachability problem, let $k \geq 1$ be a natural number, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$ be frames satisfying the IC3-Invariants. If $F_i = F_{i+1}$ for some $0 \leq i < k$, then frame F_i is an inductive strengthening of coTarget and hence Target is unreachable.*

Proof. Frame-Safety yields $F_i \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Relative inductiveness and our assumption $F_i = F_{i+1}$ yield $\Phi(F_i) \subseteq F_i$. Hence, frame F_i satisfies the conditions of an inductive strengthening of coTarget. Consequently, Lemma 3.5 implies that Target is unreachable. \square

We now go into the details of IC3[[\mathcal{A}]] shown in Figure 3.3. In line 1, we first check whether Target is reachable in 0 or 1 steps, respectively. If this is the case, the call IC3[[\mathcal{A}]](\mathcal{R}) returns reachable. Otherwise, we initialize $F_0 = I$ in line 3, thus ensuring initiality. Since we know that $I \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, we further have $F_0 = I \subseteq \text{coTarget}$ (frame-safety). Due to the failed check in line 1, we also know that $\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, i.e., we know that Target is not reachable in at most 1 step. From that, it follows that coTarget is a sound overapproximation of the locations reachable in at most 1 step such that it is sound to initialize

$F_1 = \text{coTarget}$ in line 4. The algorithm now enters the loop beginning in line 6. We call iterations of this loop *main iterations*. Notice that, at the beginning of main iteration k (beginning with $k = 1$), Lemma 3.9 and frame-safety imply that Target is not reachable in at most k steps: Frame F_k is a sound overapproximation of the locations reachable in at most k steps and, additionally, it holds that $F_k \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. The goal of main iteration k is to either discover that Target is reachable in $k + 1$ steps (and consequently returning *reachable*) or to establish that Target is *not* reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps. Determining which of these cases hold is the task of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$.

Definition 3.11 (Specification of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems. We say that $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is sound iff the following conditions hold for all $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$, all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \geq 1$, and all frames $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$: Suppose F_0, \dots, F_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants and let*

$$(\text{flag}, F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k) .$$

be the result of the call $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$.

1. If Target is reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps, then:

(a) $\text{flag} = \text{True}$.

2. If Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps, then:

(a) $\text{flag} = \text{False}$.

(b) The frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants.

(c) The successors of locations in F'_k and Target are disjoint: $\Phi(F'_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$.

(d) The frames are refined: $\forall 0 \leq i \leq k: F'_i \subseteq F_i$. △

Notice that soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is a *total* correctness property, i.e., we require that procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ always terminates when executed on inputs satisfying the assumptions from Definition 3.11. A call of the form $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ yields a flag and updated frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k . Variable flag indicates whether Target is reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps or not. If Target is reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps, the call $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ yields $\text{flag} = \text{True}$. For $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$, this means that the check in line 9 succeeds and the algorithm soundly returns *reachable*. Otherwise, i.e., if Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps, the situation is as follows. The call $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ yields $\text{flag} = \text{False}$, which means that the subsequent check in line 9 fails and that line 10 is not executed. How is the fact that Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps now reflected by the frames? First, the resulting frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k are assumed to satisfy the IC3-Invariants (Condition 2.2b). Hence, frame F'_k is a sound overapproximation of the locations reachable in at most k steps (Lemma 3.9). Moreover, Condition 2.2c implies that no successor of a location in F'_k is a location in Target . Together, this yields that Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps. $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ now proceeds by updating the frames F_0, \dots, F_k to the frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k that resulted from the call $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$. Since we have just seen that Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps, coTarget is a sound overapproximation of the locations reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps such that it is sound to initialize a new frame $F_{k+1} = \text{coTarget}$ in

line 12. Subsequently, we increase k by one in line 13 and check whether we found an inductive strengthening of coTarget proving that Target is unreachable in line 15. In case this check succeeds, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ soundly returns `unreachable` (cf. Lemma 3.10). Otherwise, the algorithm proceeds with the next iteration.

Procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is the core of algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$. Developing a suitable implementation satisfying the specification provided in Definition 3.11 is the main task when developing an IC3-style algorithm for solving reachability problems $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. These implementations make heavy use of the fact the frames F_0, \dots, F_k given to $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ satisfy the IC3-Invariants as the next sections demonstrate.

3.3 Standard IC3

After considering IC3 in a general manner, we now consider a concrete implementation for finite transition systems. In particular, we study a concrete implementation of procedure Strengthen . We call it standard IC3 as it adapted from the algorithm provided by Bradley [Bra11]. In contrast to the algorithm given in [Bra11], however, our algorithm does not work on symbolically represented transition systems. In the following, we thus consider an implementation of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{T}]$ for the class

$$\mathfrak{T} = \{(\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \mid \text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ}) \text{ is a finite transition system and } \text{Target} \subseteq L\}$$

of reachability problems for finite transition systems. The corresponding implementation of procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{T}]$ is shown in Figure 3.12 on Page 34. We explain $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{T}]$ by considering two examples: The first example demonstrates the case where Target is unreachable and the second example deals with the case where Target is reachable.

Example 3.12 Consider the following reachability problem \mathcal{R} :

Target is unreachable. Locations belonging to Target are depicted in red and locations belonging to coTarget are depicted in green. We start the run of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R})$. First, we check whether Target locations are reachable in zero or one steps, respectively. This is not the case so we initialize $F_0 = I$ and $F_1 = \text{coTarget}$ depicted in Figure 3.5 on page 28. We

now enter the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{T}]$, which invokes $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1)$. The goal of

Figure 3.5: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 1.

this invocation is to determine whether Target is reachable in at most two steps. For that, procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}]$ determines whether some predecessor of the locations in Target is reachable in at most one step. If this is not the case, then we have established that Target is not reachable in two steps. Otherwise, Target is reachable in at most two steps. The loop beginning in line 1 of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}]$ iterates over all these predecessors. Suppose it picks location l_8 first. Procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}]$ now invokes $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}](\mathcal{R}, 1, l_8, F_0, F_1)$ to determine whether location l_8 is reachable in at most 1 step.

Procedure $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ does so by exploiting the fact that the frames satisfy the IC3-Invariants: In order to determine whether some location $l \in F_i$ is reachable in at most i steps, $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ checks whether there is a predecessor l' of l in frame F_{i-1} , i.e., whether $l \in \Phi(F_{i-1})$. If this is not the case, then the IC3-Invariants imply that l cannot be reachable in at most i steps since F_{i-1} is a sound overapproximation of the locations reachable in at most $i - 1$ steps. Otherwise, i.e., if there is a predecessor l' of l with $l' \in F_{i-1}$, then $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ proceeds recursively to determine whether l' is reachable in at most $i - 1$ steps or whether it can be removed from F_{i-1} . If l' is reachable in at most $i - 1$ steps, then l is reachable in at most i steps and the procedure returns True. Otherwise, i.e., if all predecessors of l can be removed from F_{i-1} , then l is not reachable in at most i steps and can be removed from F_i . Notice that proceeding this way ensures that the updated frames satisfy the IC3-Invariants: We remove a location from some frame F_i only if we removed all predecessors from F_{i-1} . Hence, we never violate relative inductiveness. $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ essentially performs a recursive backward depth-first search from l . If, during this backward search, $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ is invoked on some initial state, then a path from that initial state to l of length at most i is found such that $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ returns True, which is then propagated to the top-level invocation of the procedure.

To determine whether l_8 is reachable in at most one step, $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ now considers all predecessors of l_8 in F_0 . Since there is no such predecessor, l_8 is not reachable in at most one step and can thus be removed from F_1 . The call to procedure $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathcal{I}]$ now returns False and the loop of procedure Strengthen selects

Figure 3.6: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 2.

l_7 as the next predecessor of Target. The call $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 1, l_7, F_0, F_1)$ removes l_7 from F_1 and returns False as l_7 has no predecessor in F_0 . Since Target is now proven to be unreachable in at most two steps, the loop of procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}]$ returns False together with the updated frames. Back in the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{I}]$, we initialize a new frame $F_2 = \text{coTarget}$: Next, we check whether two consecutive frames are equal. This is not the case and we proceed with the next iteration, which invokes $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. The goal of this invocation is to determine whether the Target locations are reachable in at most three steps. For that, the loop beginning in line 1 again considers the 2-step reachability of all predecessors of Target separately. Suppose the loop picks l_8 first such that it invokes $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 2, l_8, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. Since l_8 has no predecessor in F_1 , it is not reachable in at most two steps and can thus be removed from F_2 . $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}]$ thereby returns False and $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}]$ proceeds with the invocation $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 2, l_7, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. Since there are predecessors $l_5, l_6 \in F_1$ of l_7 , procedure $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}]$ invokes itself to determine whether these predecessors are reachable in at most one step. Both of the subsequent invocations

$\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 1, l_5, F_0, F_1, F_2)$, and

$\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 1, l_6, F_0, F_1, F_2)$

return False and remove l_5 (resp. l_6) from F_1 since neither l_5 nor l_6 has a predecessor in F_0 . Consequently, the top-level invocation of procedure $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}]$ returns False and removes l_7 from F_2 . Next, $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}]$ returns False such that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{I}]$ updates the frames and initializes a new frame $F_3 = \text{coTarget}$. We skip the next iterations and show the resulting frames instead. Notice that, after removing l_4 from F_2 in main iteration 4, we have $F_1 = F_2$. Hence $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{I}]$ terminates and returns unreachable. \triangle

Figure 3.7: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 3.

Figure 3.8: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 4.

Figure 3.9: Frames on termination of $IC3[\Xi]$.

Figure 3.10: A reachability problem where locations are associated with bit strings.

On Generalization. The preceding example demonstrates that $\text{IC3}[\Sigma]$ essentially performs a backward breadth-first search from the Target locations in order to find an inductive strengthening. The efficiency of the symbolic version of IC3 developed by Bradley stems from an ingredient which is missing in our presentation, which is called *generalization*. Recall that Bradley’s IC3 is a SAT-based technique that operates on *symbolically* represented transition systems. Proceeding in this incremental fashion allows to exploit the symbolic encoding and the capabilities of the employed SAT solver to exclude *more* than just a single location at a time from some frame *without* enumerating these locations in a monolithic manner. This process is called generalization as the fact that a single location can be removed from some frame is “generalized” to a whole set of locations. In the following, we sketch the (simplified) idea on generalization. For further reading on generalization, we refer to [Bra11, Bra12, EMB11].

Consider the reachability problem depicted in Figure 3.10 where every location is associated with a bit string of length 4. In the first main iteration of $\text{IC3}[\Sigma]$, we have to determine whether location 1101 is reachable in at most 1 step. This is not the case. Before we remove location 1101 from F_1 , we now try to *generalize*. For that, we replace some bits in the bit string 1101 by “don’t cares” D . For instance, consider the bit string $DD01$ obtained from 1101 by substituting the first two bits from the left by a D . We call such a bit string an *extended bit string*. This extended bit string represents a *set* of locations, namely all locations that end with 01. Since none of the locations in $\{0001, 0101, 1001, 1101\}$ are reachable in at most 1 step, we remove all of them from F_1 . Notice that generalizing further is not possible. Adding an additional D yielding the extended bit string $DDD1$ represents a set which contains location 0011 reachable in at most 1 step.

In general, given a location of the form $b_1 \dots b_n$ that is to be removed from some frame F_i for $i \geq 1$, we replace bit b_1 by a D . If removing the so obtained set of locations from F_i does not violate relative inductiveness, then we continue generalizing by gradually replacing the bits b_2, b_3, \dots by D s. After every replacement, we check whether removing the corresponding set of locations from F_i violates relative inductiveness. Finally, we remove the last set of locations from F_i whose removal did not violate relative

Figure 3.11: A reachability problem and the frames computed by $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{F}]$.

inductiveness.

We stress to important aspects regarding this generalization technique. First, the symbolic encoding of the transition systems determines for each location of the form $b_1 \dots b_n$ which sets of locations we consider for generalization, since gradually substituting the bits b_1, b_2, \dots uniquely determines these sets. Second, given an extended bit string B and the respective set of locations Gen , in the symbolic version of IC3, a *single* SAT query suffices to determine whether removing set Gen from frame F_i violates relative inductiveness. Hence, it is neither necessary to enumerate locations when (1) determining candidates for generalization nor (2) to determine whether removing these candidates from some frame violates relative inductiveness. Notice that this is not possible in a setup where locations are represented explicitly. This form of generalization requires some kind of symbolic representation.

Example 3.13 Consider the reachability problem depicted in Figure 3.11 where Target is reachable. We start the run $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{F}](\mathcal{R})$. The frames F_0, F_1 resulting from the initialization phase are depicted on the left-hand side of the Figure. We now enter the main loop of procedure $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{F}]$ and invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{F}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1)$. The goal is to determine whether Target is reachable in at most two steps. Therefore, we iterate over the predecessors l_3, l_2 of Target and check their 1-step reachability. Since neither l_3 nor l_2 is reachable in at most 1 step, we remove these locations from F_1 . Back in the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{F}]$, we initialize a new frame $F_2 = \text{coTarget}$ and check whether two frames are equal. The frames at the beginning of main iteration 2 are depicted on the right-hand side of Figure 3.11. We proceed with the next iteration and invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{F}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2)$ with the goal of determining whether Target is reachable in at most three steps. Considering the 2-step reachability of l_3 first, the invocation $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{F}](\mathcal{R}, 2, l_3, F_0, F_1, F_2)$ returns False and removes l_3 from F_2 as it has no predecessor in F_1 . Next, we consider

l_2 and proceed by executing $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 2, l_2, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. Since l_2 has a predecessor l_1 in F_1 , we recursively check the 1-step reachability of l_1 . Again, l_1 has a predecessor l_0 in F_0 . We thus need to check the 0-step reachability of l_0 . This is done by invoking $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}](\mathcal{R}, 0, l_0, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. This invocation returns True since l_0 is clearly reachable in zero steps. This result is now propagated to the top-level invocation of $\text{BlockLocationInFrame}[\mathfrak{I}]$ by $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}]$ as l_0 being reachable in zero steps implies that l_1 is reachable in one step and therefore l_2 is reachable in two steps. Hence $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{I}]$ returns True as it found a counterexample path from an initial location to a Target location. Finally, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{I}]$ returns **reachable**. \triangle

Algorithm 2: Strengthen $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ **Data:**

1. A reachability problem $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{T}$.
2. Frames F_0, \dots, F_k with $k \geq 1$ satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

Result: According to Definition 3.11.

```

1 while  $\exists l \in F_k : \text{Succ}(l) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$  do
2   | (flag,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
3   |   BlockLocationInFrame $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}, k, l, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ ;
4   | if flag then
5   |   | return (True,  $\_$ );
6 end
7 return (False,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ );

```

Algorithm 3: BlockLocationInFrame $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}, i, l, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ **Data:**

1. A reachability problem $\mathcal{R} = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{T}$.
2. A natural number $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $0 \leq i \leq k$.
3. A location $l \in F_i$.
4. Frames $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq L$ with $k \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

```

1 if  $i = 0$  then
2   | return True
3 while  $\exists l' \in F_{i-1} : l \in \text{Succ}(l')$  do
4   | (flag,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ )
5   |    $\leftarrow$  BlockLocationInFrame $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}, i-1, l', F_0, \dots, F_k)$ ;
6   | if flag then
7   |   | return (True,  $\_$ );
8 end
9 return (False,  $F_1, \dots, F_i \setminus \{l\}$ );

```

Figure 3.12: Implementation of procedure Strengthen $[\mathfrak{T}]$ for finite transition systems.

3.4 Standard Backward IC3

In the previous section, we have seen that standard IC3 basically performs a backward breadth-first search from the Target locations in order to find an inductive strengthening of coTarget. Such an inductive strengthening then expresses that no matter in which initial location we start, we will never reach a Target location. For our intuitive understanding of IC3 for probabilistic systems developed in the next chapter, it is useful to

consider the dual approach we coin standard *backward* IC3.

Standard backward IC3 performs a forward-breadth first search from the initial locations in order to find an inductive invariant expressing the following: No matter in which Target location l we start, we never *backward* reach an initial location from l . A frame F_i in standard backward IC3 thus overapproximates the backward reachable locations from Target locations in at most i steps. Put differently, frame F_i contains at least all locations that (forward) reach a location in Target in at most i steps. Technically, we use the same implementation of IC3 as we considered in the last section, i.e., the implementation of procedure Strengthen $[\mathfrak{T}]$ given in Figure 3.12 on Page 34. However, instead of invoking IC3 $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R})$ for $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$, we invoke IC3 $[\mathfrak{T}](\mathcal{R}_{\text{rev}})$, where \mathcal{R}_{rev} is the reversed reachability problem of \mathcal{R} :

Definition 3.14 (Reversed Reachability Problem). *Let $\mathcal{R} = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{T}$ be a reachability problem with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$. We define*

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{rev}} = (\text{TS}_{\text{rev}}, I) \quad \text{with} \quad \text{TS}_{\text{rev}} = (L, \text{Target}, \text{Pre})$$

as the reversed reachability problem obtained from swapping Target locations and initial locations and by reversing the transitions in TS. That is, $\text{Pre}: L \mapsto 2^L$ is defined as

$$\text{Pre}(l) = \{l' \in L \mid l \in \text{Succ}(l')\} .$$

Furthermore, we define $\text{coTarget}_{\text{rev}} = L \setminus I$. △

Example 3.15. Consider the following reachability problem \mathcal{R} :

The reversed reachability problem \mathcal{R}_{rev} is given by:

Example 3.16 Consider the reachability problem depicted in Figure 3.13. First, we check whether from a Target location some initial location is backward reachable in zero or one steps. This is equivalent to determining whether from an initial location we (forward) reach a Target location in zero or one steps. After that, we initialize $F_0 = \text{Target}$

Figure 3.13: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 1.

and $F_1 = \text{coTarget}_{\text{rev}} = L \setminus I$. We now enter the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{I}]$ and invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}](\mathcal{R}_{\text{rev}}, F_0, F_1)$. The goal is to determine whether an initial location is backward reachable from a Target location in at most two steps. Phrased equivalently, we need to determine whether a Target location is forward reachable from an initial location in at most two steps. For that, we consider each successor l of an initial location and determine whether from l there is a Target location reachable in at most one step. Let us consider l_2 first. Since l_2 has no successor in F_0 , it does not reach a Target location in one step and can therefore be removed from F_1 . The same holds for l_3 . Procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}]$ returns False and the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{I}]$ initializes a new frame F_2 .

$\text{IC3}[\mathcal{I}]$ proceeds with the next iteration and invokes $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}](\mathcal{R}_{\text{rev}}, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. The goal is to determine whether from an initial location we reach a Target location in at most three steps. Again, we consider each successor of an initial location separately. Since l_2 has no successor in F_1 and since F_1 contains at least all locations that reach a Target location in at most one step, from l_2 we cannot reach a Target location in at most two steps. Therefore, l_2 can be removed from F_2 . For l_3 , the situation is different: l_3 does have a successor l_4 in F_1 . We thus need to determine whether from l_4 we reach a Target location in one step. Since l_4 has no successor in F_0 , this is not the case and hence l_4 can be removed from F_1 . Consequently, l_3 can be removed from F_2 such that $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}]$ returns False. Procedure $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{I}]$ now initializes a new frame $F_3 = \text{coTarget}_{\text{rev}}$ (Figure 3.15).

Proceeding with the next main iteration, we invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{I}](\mathcal{R}_{\text{rev}}, F_0, F_1, F_2, F_3)$.

Figure 3.14: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 2.

Figure 3.15: Frames at the beginning of main iteration 3.

Figure 3.16: Frames on termination of $\text{IC3}[[\mathcal{T}]]$.

The goal is now to determine whether from an initial location we reach a Target location in at most four steps. We skip the details of this iterations and depict the resulting frames in Figure 3.16. Since $F_1 = F_2$, we found an inductive strengthening $\text{Inv} = F_1$ of $\text{coTarget}_{\text{rev}}$ and $\text{IC3}[[\mathcal{T}]]$ consequently returns *unreachable*. The inductive strengthening Inv now satisfies initiation and consecution w.r.t. the reversed reachability problem \mathcal{R}_{rev} . That is, all Target locations are elements of Inv (initiation) and for all $l \in \text{Inv}$, every predecessor l' of l is an elements of Inv again (consecution). Hence, no initial location is backward reachable from a location in Target.

3.5 Soundness and Termination

In this section, we prove that soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[[\mathcal{A}]]$ implies soundness of $\text{IC3}[[\mathcal{A}]]$. Furthermore, we provide theorems characterizing the termination behavior of $\text{IC3}[[\mathcal{A}]](\mathcal{R})$ for reachability problems \mathcal{R} where Target is reachable (Theorem 3.19) and for reachability problems \mathcal{R} with a finite set of locations (Theorem 3.20). Theorem 3.20 is similar to Theorem 1 in [HB12] but tailored to our setup.

Before proving that soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ implies soundness of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$, we first show that the IC3-Invariants are loop invariants for the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ provided that $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ satisfies its specification.

Lemma 3.17. *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems and let $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. Furthermore, assume algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ employs a sound implementation of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$. Then the IC3-Invariants are loop invariants for the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$. More precisely, the frames F_0, \dots, F_i at the beginning of main iteration i of the run $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ satisfy the IC3-Invariants*

Proof. First, we show that F_0 and F_1 satisfy the IC3-Invariants at the beginning of the main loop. After that, we show that if the IC3-Invariants hold at the beginning of an iteration of the main loop, then they also hold at the end.

The IC3-Invariants hold at the beginning of the main loop

Initiality. After line 3, it holds that $F_0 = I$.

Frame-Safety. Due to the check in line 1, we know

$$I \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset \quad \text{which implies} \quad I \subseteq \text{coTarget} .$$

Moreover, after lines 3 and 4 it holds that $F_0 = I$ and $F_1 = \text{coTarget}$. Together, this yields

$$F_0 = I \subseteq \text{coTarget} \quad \text{and} \quad F_1 = \text{coTarget} \subseteq \text{coTarget} .$$

Chain-Property. The statement above immediately yields $F_0 \subseteq F_1$.

Relative Inductiveness. After the check in line 1, we know

$$\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset \quad \text{implying} \quad \Phi(I) \subseteq \text{coTarget} .$$

This and the fact that after lines 3 and 4 it holds that $F_0 = I$ and $F_1 = \text{coTarget}$ then yield

$$\Phi(F_0) = \Phi(I) \subseteq \text{coTarget} .$$

The main loop preserves the IC3-Invariants

Suppose the main loop is at the beginning of iteration i storing the frames F_0, \dots, F_i . We have to show that the frames $\tilde{F}_0, \dots, \tilde{F}_i, \tilde{F}_{i+1}$ resulting from that iteration satisfy the IC3-Invariants, too. For that, we assume that Target is not reachable in at most $i + 1$ steps since otherwise the loop terminates. Definition 3.11 implies that the invocation of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ in lines 7 and 8 yields

$$(\text{False}, F'_0, \dots, F'_i) = \text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k) .$$

Afterwards, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ updates the frames to those that resulted from $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ and initializes a new frame $F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget}$. Hence, we need to show that $F'_0, \dots, F'_i, F_{i+1}$ with $F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget}$ satisfy the IC3-Invariants.

Initiality. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ preserves the IC3-Invariants, we have $F'_0 = I$.

Frame-Safety. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ preserves the IC3-Invariants, we have $F'_0, \dots, F'_i \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Moreover, after line 11 it holds that $F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$.

Chain-Property. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ preserves the IC3-Invariants, we have $F'_0 \subseteq \dots \subseteq F'_i$. It thus remains to show that $F'_i \subseteq F_{i+1}$ holds. Due to Frame-Safety, we have $F'_i \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Since $F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget}$, we get $F'_i \subseteq \text{coTarget} = F_{i+1}$.

Relative Inductiveness. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ preserves the IC3-Invariants, we have $\Phi(F'_j) \subseteq F'_{j+1}$ for all $0 \leq j < i$. It thus remains to show that $\Phi(F'_i) \subseteq F_{i+1}$. The specification of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ (Definition 3.11) yields $\Phi(F'_i) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$ and thus $\Phi(F'_i) \subseteq \text{coTarget}$. Since $F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget}$, we conclude

$$\Phi(F'_i) \subseteq \text{coTarget} = F_{i+1}.$$

This completes the proof. □

With this result at hand, soundness of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ follows by a case distinction.

Theorem 3.18 (Soundness of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems and suppose $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ employs $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$. If $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is sound, then $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is sound.*

Proof. This follows from the fact that the main loop preserves the IC3-Invariants by Lemma 3.17. There are three situations that cause the loop to terminate: either it terminates in line 1, line 9, or line 12. We consider these cases separately.

Case 1: the loop terminates in line 1. We have to show that Target is *reachable*. If $I \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, then Target is reachable in at most 0 steps. Similarly, if $\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, then Target is reachable in at most 1 step.

Case 2: the loop terminates in line 9. We have to show that Target is *reachable*. Suppose the loop terminates in main iteration k . Since the sequence of frames F_0, \dots, F_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants and $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ returned $\text{flag} = \text{True}$, the specification of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ implies that Target is reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps.

Case 3: the loop terminates in line 12. We have to show that Target is *unreachable*. Since the check in line 14 succeeded, we know that in the current sequence of frames F_0, \dots, F_k there are two consecutive frames F_i and F_{i+1} with $F_i = F_{i+1}$. Furthermore, F_0, \dots, F_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants by Lemma 3.17. In particular, relative inductiveness and frame-safety yield

$$\Phi(F_i) \subseteq F_{i+1} \quad \text{and} \quad F_i \subseteq \text{coTarget}.$$

The first statement and the assumption $F_i = F_{i+1}$ imply $\Phi(F_i) \subseteq F_i$. Due to this and the second statement from above, F_i satisfies the condition of an inductive strengthening of coTarget (Definition 3.4). Hence, by Lemma 3.5, we have $\text{Reach} \subseteq \text{coTarget}$ and therefore, Target is unreachable.

□

The next theorem shows that, given a sound implementation of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ and $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$ where Target is reachable, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ terminates independent of whether the underlying transition system is finite or infinite. Intuitively, this is the case because Target being reachable implies that there is a k such that $\Phi^k(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, i.e., Target is reachable within finitely many steps. Hence, on main iteration $k - 1$ of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$, the call $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_{k-1})$ returns True which yields $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ to return reachable.

Theorem 3.19 (Termination on Reachability). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems and suppose $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ employs a sound implementation of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$. Furthermore, let $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$. If Target is reachable, then the call $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R})$ terminates.*

Proof. We provide an upper bound on the number of main loop iterations. Due to Lemma 3.3, there is a $j \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\Phi^j(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$. We claim that the algorithm terminates in iteration $j - 1$. At the beginning of that iteration, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ stores the frames F_0, \dots, F_{j-1} satisfying the IC3-Invariants by Lemma 3.17. Since Target is reachable in at most j steps, the subsequent invocation of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_{j-1})$ then yields $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ (Definition 3.11) such that the check in line 9 succeeds. Consequently, $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ terminates returning reachable. □

Next, we show that if \mathfrak{A} consists solely of reachability problems with a *finite* underlying transition system and if $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is sound, then it terminates for all $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$ no matter how $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is implemented. If Target is reachable, then this follows already from Theorem 3.19. If Target is unreachable, then the underlying TS of \mathcal{R} being finite implies that it must be the case that eventually two consecutive frames collapse.

Theorem 3.20 (Completeness for Finite Domains). *Let \mathfrak{A} be a class of reachability problems and let $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ be sound. If L is finite for all $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$, then $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ is complete.*

Proof. By contradiction. Assume there is an $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{A}$ with L finite and such that the main loop does *not* terminate. Since the stored sequence of frames always satisfies the IC3-Invariants by Lemma 3.17, the invocation of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{A}]$ always terminates and the main loop of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{A}]$ always reaches the next iteration. Now consider the end of main iteration j and the computed sequence of frames F_0, \dots, F_{j+1} . Since the loop does not terminate, the check in line 14 failed, hence

$$\forall 0 \leq i < j: F_i \neq F_{i+1}. \quad (3.1)$$

Moreover, the frames satisfy the Chain-Property:

$$\forall 0 \leq i < j: F_i \subseteq F_{i+1} \quad (3.2)$$

Clearly, Statements 3.1 and 3.2 imply that the frames form a strictly ascending chain:

$$\forall 0 \leq i < j: F_i \subset F_{i+1}$$

Since j is unbounded, the loop produces an infinite *and* strictly ascending chain over the finite domain L , which is a contradiction. □

Chapter 4

IC3 for Markov Chains

We are now in a position to develop IC3 for *explicitly represented* and *finite* Markov chains. For that, the framework for solving reachability problems of transition systems developed in the last chapter plays a central role. We translate the quantitative variant of reachability in Markov chains to reachability problems of *infinite* transition systems. After that, we develop an implementation of procedure Strengthen tailored to those reachability problems that arise from finite Markov chains. Even though we technically operate on an infinite transition system, the resulting algorithm is strongly connected to the notions of reachability probabilities in the given Markov chain.

4.1 Algorithm IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$

Assumptions. In what follows, we assume a finite Markov chain $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$. Furthermore, given $G \subseteq S$, we assume that we have the set $S_{>0} = \{s \in S \mid \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond G) > 0\}$ of states that reach a state in G with a strictly positive probability and require that $s_I \in S_{>0}$. These assumptions are crucial for the termination behavior of the algorithm developed in this section. In Section 4.4, we discuss an extension of IC3 for finite Markov chains that allows to drop the assumption of knowing the set $S_{>0}$ upfront. Finally, we assume that all states $s \in G$ are *absorbing*.

We develop an algorithm for the quantitative variant of reachability in Markov chains:

Given a finite Markov chain $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$, a set of goal states G ,
and a rational threshold $\lambda \in (0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$, does it hold that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$?

Before we start developing that algorithm, we compare the above problem with reachability problems for finite transition systems targeted by *standard IC3*. In Chapter 3.1 we have seen that for $\mathcal{R} \in \mathfrak{T}$ it either holds that Target is reachable, or that Target is unreachable. Analogously, given an MC \mathcal{C} , a set of goal states G , and a threshold $\lambda \in (0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$, it either holds that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$ or $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$. We compare these cases separately.

Figure 4.1: A sample Markov chain and the set of goal states $G = \{s_5\}$. We have $\Pr^C(\diamond G) = 13/30$, $S_{>0} = \{s_I, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5\}$, and $S_{=0} = \{s_6\}$.

In order to determine that some location $l \in \text{Target}$ is reachable in a finite transition system, it suffices to find a *single* path from some initial location to location l . For Markov chains, the situation is different: Recall from Chapter 2.3 that the probability to eventually reach a state in G is defined as the sum of the probabilities of all finite paths that start in s_I and end in a state in G , i.e.,

$$\Pr^C(\diamond G) = \sum_{s_0 \dots s_n \in \text{Paths}_{\text{fin}}(\mathcal{C}) \cap (S \setminus G)^* G} P(s_0 \dots s_n).$$

Hence, a single path from s_I to a state in G does not suffice in general to determine that $\Pr^C(\diamond G) > \lambda$. To demonstrate this, consider MC $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ and the set of goal states $G = \{s_5\}$ depicted in Figure 4.1 as a running example. The probability to eventually reach G is given by $\Pr^C(\diamond G) = 13/30 \approx 0.433$. Now suppose we are given $\lambda = 0.3$, i.e., $\Pr^C(\diamond G) > \lambda$. We need to determine the probabilities of the *three* paths $\pi_1 = s_I s_1 s_3 s_5$, $\pi_2 = s_I s_1 s_3 s_1 s_3 s_5$, and $\pi_3 = s_I s_2 s_4 s_5$ to get that $P(\pi_1) + P(\pi_2) + P(\pi_3) > \lambda$. It is not possible to establish that with only two paths or less.

Similarly, if Target is unreachable in a given finite transition system, it suffices to show that no path starting in an initial location leads to a Target location. In contrast to that, in order to show that $\Pr^C(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$, we have to prove that the sum of the probabilities of *all* (possibly infinitely many) finite paths from s_I to a state in G does not exceed λ . Here, our algorithm exploits the fact that if $\Pr^C(\diamond G) < \lambda$, then it suffices to find *finitely many* paths from the initial state s_I to a state in $S_{=0}$ (if $\Pr^C(\diamond G) = \lambda$, this does not hold in general). Given n finite paths π_1, \dots, π_n from s_I to a state in $S_{=0}$ with respective probabilities $P(\pi_1), \dots, P(\pi_n)$, we obtain an upper bound on $\Pr^C(\diamond G)$ given by

$$\Pr^C(\diamond G) \leq 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P(\pi_i).$$

Figure 4.2: A reachable fragment of the reachability problem $\mathcal{R}_{>0}$ induced by MC \mathcal{C} , G , and λ from Figure 4.1. Locations v are represented in vector notation. The topmost entry corresponds to $v[s_I]$, the second entry from above corresponds to $v[s_1]$, and so on.

The intuitive reason is that once we are “trapped” in a state in $S_{=0}$, we have no chance to reach a state in G . Hence, any *lower* bound on the probability of reaching a state in $S_{=0}$ yields an *upper* bound on $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G)$ (and vice versa). In a nutshell, whereas in standard IC3 it suffices to reason qualitatively, IC3 for finite Markov chains must incorporate *quantitative* reasoning.

Let us now develop IC3 for Markov chains. The crucial observation for our approach is that the problem of determining whether $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$ holds for some MC \mathcal{C} , G , and λ can be equivalently phrased as a reachability problem of an *infinite* transition system.

Definition 4.1 (Reachability Problem induced by MC \mathcal{C} , G , and λ). *Let \mathcal{C} be an MC, $G \subseteq S$, and let $\lambda \in (0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$. The reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$ induced by \mathcal{C} , G , and λ is defined as*

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}), \text{ where:}$$

1. TS = (L, I, Succ) is an infinite transition system, where:

(a) The set of locations is the set of all assignments from states in $S_{>0}$ to probabilities, i.e.,

$$L = [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}.$$

(b) The set of initial locations is the singleton $I = \{v_0\}$, where

$$v_0[s] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in G \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(c) The successor function Succ is induced by $\Upsilon_{>0}$, i.e., $\text{Succ}(v) = \{\Upsilon_{>0}(v)\}$.

2. Target is the set of all locations v with $v[s_I] > \lambda$, i.e.,

$$\text{Target} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid v[s_I] > \lambda\}.$$

Notice that coTarget is the set of all locations v with $v[s_I] \leq \lambda$, i.e.,

$$\text{coTarget} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid v[s_I] \leq \lambda\} .$$

Finally, we denote by

$$\mathfrak{C}_{>0} = \{\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \mid \mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P) \text{ is an MC, } G \subseteq S, \text{ and } \lambda \in (0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}\}$$

the class of reachability problems induced by finite MCs (with knowledge of $S_{>0}$). \triangle

The locations of the transition systems as defined in Definition 4.1 are denoted by v and variations thereof. Now let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$. Transition system TS has a single initial location v_0 , i.e., it starts with the 0-step reachability probabilities, and every location has exactly one successor. The successor of location v_0 is given by $v_1 = \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)$, i.e., the 1-step reachability probabilities. A reachable fragment of such a transition system is depicted in Figure 4.2 on page 43. In general, the successor of location v_k is given by $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_k) = v_{k+1}$ for all $k \geq 0$. Hence, the set of locations reachable in at most k steps $\text{Reach}^{\leq k}$ is given by

$$\text{Reach}^{\leq k} = \{\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_0) \mid 0 \leq i \leq k\} .$$

This justifies the definition of Target and coTarget , respectively: If Target is unreachable, then we have $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$. Conversely, if Target is reachable, then $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$.

Lemma 4.2. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$. Target is unreachable iff $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$.*

Proof. We first show that if Target is unreachable, then $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$. From our above reasoning it follows that

$$\text{Reach} = \sup_k \text{Reach}^{\leq k} = \{\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0) \mid k \geq 0\} .$$

Since Target is unreachable, we have $(\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)) [s_I] \leq \lambda$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $v_\lambda \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with

$$v_\lambda[s] = \begin{cases} \lambda, & \text{if } s = s_I \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The map v_λ is an upper bound on $\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0) \leq v_\lambda$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, where \leq is to be understood point-wise. Consequently,

$$\sup_k \Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0) \leq v_\lambda .$$

This yields $(\sup_k \Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)) [s_I] \leq \lambda$ and thus $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$.

Next, we show that if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$, then Target is unreachable. $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$ implies $(\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)) [s_I] \leq \lambda$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Hence, we have

$$\{\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0) \mid k \geq 0\} \cap \{v \in S_{>0} \mid v[s_I] > \lambda\} = \emptyset ,$$

which implies $\text{Reach} \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$. \square

Algorithm 4: IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ ($\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$)

Data: A reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathcal{C}_{>0}$.
Result: According to Definition 3.7.

```

1 if  $v_0[s_I] > \lambda$  or  $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda$  then
2   | return reachable;
3  $F_0 \leftarrow \{v_0\}$ ;
4  $F_1 \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
5  $k \leftarrow 1$ ;
6 while True do
7   | (flag,  $F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
8   |   Strengthen $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ ( $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, \dots, F_k$ );
9   | if flag then
10  |   | return reachable;
11  |   |  $F_0, \dots, F_k \leftarrow F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ ;
12  |   |  $F_{k+1} \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
13  |   |  $k \leftarrow k + 1$ ;
14  |   | if  $\exists 0 \leq i < k: F_i = F_{i+1}$  then
15  |   |   | return unreachable;
16 end

```

Figure 4.3: IC3 for finite Markov chains. Here $\Upsilon_{>0}$ denotes the restricted reachability probability operator determined by the underlying MC \mathcal{C} and the set of goal states G .

We now develop an implementation of IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ by providing an implementation of procedure Strengthen $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$. For that, we employ the framework presented in Chapter 3.

First, we study some properties of the frames in IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$. Recall from standard backward IC3 that frame F_i contains at least all locations from which we reach a Target location in at most i steps. Similarly, in IC3 for finite Markov chains, frame F_i contains at least all reachability probabilities to reach a goal state in G from state s in at most i steps for all $s \in S_{>0}$. Consider the MC \mathcal{C} and the set of goal states $G = \{s_5\}$ from Figure 4.1 on page 42. A fragment of the reachable locations of the corresponding reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$ is depicted in Figure 4.2 on page 43. Suppose IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ computed the frames $F_0, F_1, F_2 \subseteq [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$. Each frame is a set of assignments from states in $S_{>0}$ to probabilities. Now recall from Lemma 3.9 that—since the frames must satisfy the IC3-Invariants—every frame F_i overapproximates the locations reachable in at most i steps. If $v \in F_i$, then we say that v is a *candidate for the i -step reachability probabilities*. Formally, given frames F_0, \dots, F_k computed by IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$, we have

$$F_i \supseteq \{\Upsilon_{>0}^j(v_0) \mid 0 \leq j \leq i\} \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq i \leq k.$$

IC3 for finite Markov chains is depicted in Figure 4.3. We first consider the initialization phase from lines 1–5. Suppose we invoke IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ on the reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target})$ with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ induced by some MC \mathcal{C} , G , and λ . In lines 1–2, we check whether the probability to reach a state in G in zero or one steps exceeds the threshold λ already, i.e., whether it holds that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) > \lambda$. This

Algorithm 5: Strengthen $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ ($\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, \dots, F_k$)

Data:

1. A reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$ with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$.
2. Frames F_0, \dots, F_k with $k \geq 1$ satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

Result: According to Definition 3.11.

```

1 if  $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$  then
2   | return (False,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ )
3 (flag,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
4   BlockLocationsInFrame $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ ( $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, \dots, F_k$ );
5 if flag then
6   | return (True,  $\_$ );
7 return (False,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ );

```

Algorithm 6: BlockLocationsInFrame $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ ($\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k$)

Data:

1. A reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$ with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$.
2. A natural number $i \geq 1$.
3. Frames F_0, \dots, F_k with $k \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

Result: According to Lemma 4.9

```

1 if  $k = 0$  then
2   | return (True,  $\_$ );
3 if  $\Phi(F_{k-1}) \cap \text{Exclude}^i \neq \emptyset$  then
4   | (flag,  $F_0, \dots, F_{k-1}$ )  $\leftarrow$ 
5     BlockLocationsInFrame $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ ( $\mathcal{R}_{>0}, i + 1, F_0, \dots, F_{k-1}$ );
6   | if flag then
7     | return (True,  $\_$ );
8   |  $F_1, \dots, F_k \leftarrow F_1 \setminus \text{Exclude}^i, \dots, F_k \setminus \text{Exclude}^i$ ;
9 return (False,  $F_0, \dots, F_k$ );

```

Figure 4.4: Implementation of procedure Strengthen $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ for finite Markov chains. Here $\Upsilon_{>0}$ denotes the restricted reachability probability operator of \mathcal{C} and G . Φ denotes the reachability operator induced by TS.

coincides with the framework developed in Chapter 3: We check whether $I \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$ or $\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$. Since $I = \{v_0\}$ and $\text{Target} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid v[s_I] > \lambda\}$, the former is equivalent to $v_0[s_I] > \lambda$ (line 1). Furthermore, $\Phi(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$ is equivalent to $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda$ (line 1). If one of these cases holds, then $\Pr^C(\diamond G) > \lambda$ and hence $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ returns reachable (line 2).

If we reach line 3, we have established that $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) \leq \lambda$. We then initialize $F_0 = I = \{v_0\}$ (line 3) and $F_1 = \text{coTarget} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid v[s_I] \leq \lambda\}$ (line 4). Notice that since $v_0[s_I] \leq \lambda$ and $v_1[s_I] = \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[s_I] \leq \lambda$, we have $\{v_0, v_1\} \subseteq F_1$, i.e., F_1 is a sound overapproximation of the reachability probabilities for up to one step. Let us compare to standard backward IC3. There, we first check whether from an initial location we reach a Target location in zero or one steps, respectively. Analogously, $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ checks whether the probability to reach a goal state from state s_I in zero or one steps is greater than λ .

$\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ now enters the main loop beginning in line 6. Let us therefore consider procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ depicted in Figure 4.4 on page 46—the core of $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$. Denote by $\text{ReachStates}^{\equiv i} \subseteq S_{>0}$ those states in $S_{>0}$ that are reachable from s_I in exactly i steps. First, we define the following:

Definition 4.3. Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC and let $G \subseteq S$. Furthermore, let $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$. Then we call $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I]$ the probability to reach a state in G from s_I in at most $i + j$ steps assuming that the probability to reach a state in G from state s in at most j steps is given by $v[s]$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\equiv i}$. \triangle

The probability $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I]$ solely depends on the reachability probabilities $v[s]$ for $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\equiv i}$. The idea underlying the above definition is that $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I]$ is equal to $\sum_{s \in S_{>0}} p_s \cdot v[s]$, where p_s is the probability to reach state s from state s_I in exactly i steps, and where $v[s]$ is the assumed probability to reach a state in G from state s in at most j steps for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\equiv i}$. Overall, this yields the probability to reach a state in G from state s_I in at most $i + j$ steps under the assumption that we reach a state in G from state s in at most j steps with probability $v[s]$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\equiv i}$.

Example 4.4. Reconsider MC \mathcal{C} and the set of goal states $G = \{s_5\}$ from Figure 4.1. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_I] &= 0.25 \cdot v[s_1] + 0.75 \cdot v[s_2] \\ \text{and} \quad \Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)[s_I] &= 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot v[s_3] + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot v[s_2] + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot v[s_4]. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\text{ReachStates}^{\equiv 1} = \{s_1, s_2\}$ and $\text{ReachStates}^{\equiv 2} = \{s_2, s_3, s_4\}$. Now let $v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $v'[s_1] = v'[s_2] = 1$. Then the probability $\Upsilon_{>0}(v')[s_I]$ to reach a state in G from s_I in at most 2 steps assuming that the probability to reach a state in G from states s_1, s_2 in at most 1 step is given by $v'[s_1]$ and $v'[s_2]$, respectively, is given by

$$\Upsilon_{>0}(v')[s_I] = 0.25 \cdot 1 + 0.75 \cdot 1 = 1.$$

Now let $v'[s_3] = v'[s_2] = v'[s_4] = 1$. The probability $\Upsilon_{>0}^2(v')[s_I]$ to reach a state in G from s_I in at most 3 steps assuming that the probability to reach a state in G from states s_3, s_2, s_4 in at most 1 step is given by $v'[s_3]$, $v'[s_2]$, and $v'[s_4]$, respectively, is given by

$$\Upsilon_{>0}^2(v')[s_I] = 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot 1 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot 1 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot 1 = 0.625.$$

Even though we assume that $v'[s] = 1$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\neq 2}$, we have $\Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)_{s_I} < 1$. The “missing” probability mass represents the probability to get trapped in a state $s \in S_{=0}$ on the way to a state in $\text{ReachStates}^{\neq 2}$. We thus obtain an upper bound on $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G)$. Furthermore, this demonstrates why we employ operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$ instead of Υ and why it is important to have the set $S_{>0}$ (respectively $S_{=0}$) at hand. The reason for obtaining the upper bound on $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G)$ is that operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$ does not take states in $S_{=0}$ into account. \triangle

In standard backward IC3, $\text{Strengthen}[\Upsilon](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ determines whether from an initial location we reach a target location in at most $k + 1$ steps. For that, it considers the direct successors of the initial locations and determines whether these are reachable in at most k steps. This is analogous to what procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ does. That is, the goal of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ is to determine whether the probability to reach a goal state from initial state s_I in at most $k + 1$ steps is greater than λ . For that, observe the following: Let $v'_k \in F_k$ be a candidate for the k -step reachability probabilities. The probability to reach a goal state from state s_I in at most $k + 1$ steps *assuming* that the k -step reachability probabilities are given by v'_k is given by

$$\Upsilon_{>0}(v'_k)[s_I] = \sum_{s' \in S_{>0}} P(s_I, s') \cdot v'_k[s'] .$$

This implies that determining whether it holds that $\text{Pr}^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$ boils down to determining whether we can exclude all locations v from F_k with $\Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_I] > \lambda$ while preserving the fact that F_k is a sound overapproximation of the k -step reachability probabilities. In other words, we have to determine whether the overapproximation F_k of the k -step reachability probabilities can be refined (or *strengthened*) in such a way that no $v \in F_k$ indicates that the probability to reach a state in G from state s_I in at most $k + 1$ steps is greater than λ . If this is possible, then we have established that $\text{Pr}^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$. If this is not possible, then it holds that $\text{Pr}^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) > \lambda$.

In order to determine which of these cases hold, procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ first checks whether F_k contains a $v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_I] > \lambda$ in line 1. Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v \in F_k : \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \notin \text{Target} && \text{Def. of } \Phi \text{ and Succ} \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v \in F_k : \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_I] \leq \lambda . && \text{Def. of Target} \end{aligned}$$

If this check succeeds, then we do not have to exclude any location from F_k and return $\text{flag} = \text{False}$ together with the unmodified frames F_0, \dots, F_k . Otherwise, i.e., if the check fails, then we have to determine whether we can exclude all $v \in F_k$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \text{Target}$ from F_k . The main difference to finite transition systems is that there are infinitely many such v in general. Considering every such v individually is therefore not an option.

Example 4.5. Reconsider MC $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ and the set of goal states $G = \{s_5\}$ from Figure 4.1 and let $\lambda = 0.5$. We start the run of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$. First, we check whether the probability to reach G from s_I in zero or one steps is greater than λ . This is not the case and we initialize $F_0 = \{v_0\}$ and $F_1 = \text{coTarget}$. We now enter the main loop and invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}_{>0}, F_0, F_1)$. The goal is to determine whether the probability to reach a state

in G from s_I in at most 2 steps is greater than λ . For that, we first check whether it holds that $\Phi(F_1) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$. This is equivalent to

$$\forall v \in F_1 : 0.25 \cdot v[s_1] + 0.75 \cdot v[s_2] \leq \lambda.$$

The inequation does not hold since there is a $v \in F_1$ with, e.g., $v[s_1] = v[s_2] = 1$. Hence, our overapproximation of the 1-step reachability probabilities F_1 has to be refined in order to establish that $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 2} G) \leq \lambda$ holds. Furthermore, observe that there are infinitely many $v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $0.25 \cdot v[s_1] + 0.75 \cdot v[s_2] > \lambda$. \triangle

The problem that we have to consider infinitely many locations is not new. Authors developing extensions of IC3 for software model checking [CG12, LNN15, HB12] encounter a similar situation. Instead of considering each location individually as in standard IC3, Cimatti and Griggio propose to consider *all* of these infinitely many locations at once [CG12]. We adopt this approach. That is, on main iteration k , we have to determine whether we can remove all locations in the set $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ given by

$$\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_I] > \lambda\}$$

from F_k . This is the task of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, \dots, F_k)$. As it is the case for standard (backward) IC3, we proceed recursively in order to determine whether $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_k . Assume $k > 0$. We need to determine whether removing $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ from F_k violates relative inductiveness. In IC3 for finite Markov chains, frame F_k is inductive relative to frame F_{k-1} iff

$$\forall v \in F_{k-1} : \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in F_k.$$

Hence, $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_k iff

$$\begin{aligned} & \nexists v \in F_{k-1} : \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}} \\ \text{iff} \quad & \nexists v \in F_{k-1} : \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \{v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}(v')[s_I] > \lambda\} \\ \text{iff} \quad & \nexists v \in F_{k-1} : \Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)[s_I] > \lambda. \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

In words, $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_k iff the following holds: No matter which $v \in F_{k-1}$ we choose as a candidate for the $(k-1)$ -step reachability probabilities, the probability $\Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)[s_I]$ to reach a state in G from s_I in at most $k+1$ steps assuming that the probabilities to reach a state in G from state s in at most $k-1$ steps are given by $v[s]$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\text{=2}}$ must not be greater than λ . That is, we now consider the $(k-1)$ -step reachability probabilities of states reachable in exactly two steps. If Condition 4.1 holds, then $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_k without violating relative inductiveness and we have established that $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$ holds.

Otherwise, i.e., if there is a $v \in F_{k-1}$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)[s_I] > \lambda$, then we have to recursively determine whether the set $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ given by

$$\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^2(v)[s_I] > \lambda\}$$

can be removed from F_{k-1} (line 5 of procedure $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$). If it is possible to remove $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ from F_{k-1} while preserving the fact that F_{k-1} is a sound overapproximation of the $(k-1)$ -step reachability probabilities, then $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed

from F_k (line 8) and we have established that $\Pr^C (s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$. Otherwise, i.e., if $\text{Exclude}^{=2}$ cannot be removed from F_{k-1} , then $\text{Exclude}^{=1}$ cannot be removed from F_k and hence $\Pr^C (s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) > \lambda$. In this situation, $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ such that $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ and $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns *reachable*. This case is treated on the next page.

Observe again the similarities to standard backward IC3: To determine whether we reach a Target location from some initial location in at most $k + 1$ steps, we determine whether some direct successor l' of some initial location reaches a Target location in at most k steps. For that, in turn, we identify whether from some direct successor l'' of some l' we reach a Target location in at most $k - 1$ steps. IC3 for finite Markov chains behaves analogously: For establishing whether $\Pr^C (s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$ holds, we determine whether we can refine the overapproximation of the k -step reachability probabilities of the direct successors s' of s_I accordingly. For that, we determine whether the $(k - 1)$ -step reachability probabilities of the direct successors s'' of each s' can be refined accordingly.

Remark. We remove $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ from F_1, \dots, F_{k-1} only for the sake of modular soundness proofs. When implementing $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, it suffices to remove $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ from F_k since $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ has been removed from F_1, \dots, F_{k-1} in the preceding iterations.

In order to complete the discussion of procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, we define:

Definition 4.6 (Exclude sets). *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$, and let $i \in \mathbb{N}$. The set $\text{Exclude}^{=i} \subseteq [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ (w.r.t. $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$) is defined as*

$$\text{Exclude}^{=i} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} . \quad \triangle$$

Suppose we are given frames $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ satisfying the IC3-Invariants and suppose that we are in procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ for establishing whether it holds that $\Pr^C (s_I \models \diamond^{\leq k+1} G) \leq \lambda$. The above explanation generalizes as follows: In order to determine whether the set $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ can be removed from some frame F_j for some $j > 0$, we invoke

$$\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_j) .$$

First, we check whether for some location $v \in F_{j-1}$ it holds that $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v) \in \text{Exclude}^{=i}$ (line 3). If this is not the case, then $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ can be removed from frame F_j without violating the IC3-Invariants (line 8). Otherwise, i.e., if $\Phi(F_{j-1}) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i} \neq \emptyset$, we recursively determine whether $\text{Exclude}^{=i+1}$ can be removed from F_{j-1} . If this succeeds, then $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ can be removed from F_j (line 8). Otherwise, we have $\text{flag} = \text{True}$, which is then propagated to the top-level invocation of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ and thus also to $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, which yields $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ to soundly return *reachable*. This is the case if $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is invoked on the single frame F_0 . Consider the invocation of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0)$ for some i . This invocation is executed only if it is necessary to exclude some locations from F_0 . Since we have to maintain initiality, i.e., $F_0 = \{v_0\}$, it is, however, not possible to remove some location from F_0 without violating the IC3-Invariants. From that, it follows that it is not possible to remove $\text{Exclude}^{=i-j}$ from F_j for all $1 \leq j \leq k$, which justifies that, in this case, $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ and propagates this to $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$.

Figure 4.5: The Markov chain from Figure 4.1.

Examples. Let us now consider examples that demonstrate $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$. In these examples, we demonstrate the execution of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ for some λ , and where $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ and $G = \{s_5\}$ are the MC and the set of goal states depicted in Figure 4.5 on page 51. For our convenience, we represent the frames by means of quantifier-free formulae over $(\mathbb{R}, +, \cdot, \leq)$ —the first order theory of the reals. By slight abuse of notation, by F_j we denote *both* the formula representing the corresponding sets of locations *and* the set of locations the formula defines. With each state $s_i \in S_{>0}$ we associate a first-order variable x_i and assume that $v \in F_j$ iff the closed formula obtained from substituting every occurrence of x_i in F_j by $v[s_i]$ for every x_i evaluates to True. For instance, if frame F_j is given by the formula

$$F_j = x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5,$$

then we have

$$v \in F_j \quad \text{iff} \quad v[s_I] \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot v[s_1] + 0.75 \cdot v[s_2] \leq 0.5.$$

Example 4.7. We start the run of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ with $\lambda = 0.5 \geq \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G)$. First, we check whether $v_0[s_I] > 0.5$ or $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[s_I] > 0.5$, i.e., whether the zero or one step reachability probability is greater than 0.5 already. This is not the case and we initialize F_0 and F_1 :

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 1:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = \text{coTarget} = x_I \leq 0.5.$$

Next, we enter the main loop and invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1)$ to determine whether $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 2} G) \leq 0.5$. For that, we call $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, F_1)$

and thereby check whether it is possible to restrict the candidates of the 1-step reachability probabilities of states in $\text{ReachStates}^{\text{=1}}$ accordingly. That is, we check whether removing the set

$$\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 0.25 \cdot v[s_1] + 0.75 \cdot v[s_2] > 0.5\}$$

from F_1 violates relative inductiveness, i.e., whether $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}} \neq \emptyset$. This is not the case and we strengthen F_1 by removing $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$, establishing that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 2} G) \leq 0.5$. After initializing a new frame $F_2 = \text{coTarget}$, we have

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 2:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\ F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ F_2 &= x_I \leq 0.5. \end{aligned}$$

We now invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2)$ with the goal of determining whether it holds that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 3} G) \leq 0.5$. For that, we check whether we can remove $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ from F_2 . Since this violates relative inductiveness, we recursively check whether the 1-step reachability probabilities of states in $\text{ReachStates}^{\text{=2}}$ can be restricted accordingly. We thus have to remove

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}} \\ &= \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot v[s_3] + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot v[s_2] + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot v[s_4] > 0.5\} \end{aligned}$$

from F_1 without violating relative inductiveness. Set $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ can be removed from F_1 , and $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_2 . After initializing a new frame $F_3 = \text{coTarget}$, we have

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 3:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\ F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ &\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.5 \\ F_2 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ F_3 &= x_I \leq 0.5. \end{aligned}$$

We invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2, F_3)$. The goal is to determine whether it holds that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 4} G) \leq 0.5$. Hence, we check whether $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be excluded from F_3 . For that, we determine whether $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ can be excluded from F_2 without violating relative inductiveness. This is the case. Hence, $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ can be excluded from F_2 and $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ can be removed from F_3 . Next, we initialize a new frame $F_4 = \text{coTarget}$:

Frames after main iteration 3:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\ F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ &\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_2 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\
&\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.5 \\
F_3 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\
F_4 &= x_I \leq 0.5 .
\end{aligned}$$

Since $F_1 = F_2$, we found an inductive strengthening of coTarget . Hence, by Lemma 4.2, we have established that $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G) \leq 0.5$ and $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ soundly returns *unreachable*. So for $\lambda = 0.5$, we need 3 iterations in order to find an inductive strengthening. The smaller the difference between λ and $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G)$, the more iterations we need for that. For this example, we have:

If $\lambda = 0.45$, then we need 5 iterations.

If $\lambda = 0.44$, then we need 7 iterations.

If $\lambda = 0.43334$, then we need 18 iterations. △

The preceding example demonstrates that—similar to standard backward IC3— $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ actually performs a breadth-first from initial state s_I : The fact that we have to maintain relative inductiveness forces the algorithm to keep removing the sets Exclude^i from F_1 for increasing $i = 1, 2, \dots$. Every removal of some set Exclude^i from F_1 restricts the candidates for the 1-step reachability probabilities of states in ReachStates^i . That is, we bound the 1-step reachability probabilities of states in ReachStates^i for increasing i until it holds that F_1 is an inductive strengthening of coTarget , i.e, until it holds that $F_1 = F_2$. If $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G) < \lambda$, this will always be the case (cf. Theorem 4.12). The intuitive reason is that, as i increases, the algorithm observes ever more paths from s_I to a state in $S_{=0}$, which eventually suffices to establish that $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G) < \lambda$.

Let us now consider an example where $\text{Pr}^C(\diamond G) > \lambda$ holds.

Example 4.8. Let $\lambda = 0.3$. We start the run of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$. Since neither $v_0[s_I] > 0.3$ nor $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0[s_I]) > 0.3$ holds, we initialize F_0 and F_1 :

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\
F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.3 .
\end{aligned}$$

The next two iterations of the main loop behave as in Example 4.7. Let us therefore skip these iterations and consider the

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 3:

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\
F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.3 \\
&\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.3 \\
F_2 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.3
\end{aligned}$$

$$F_3 = x_I \leq 0.5 .$$

Observe that $F_1 = \text{coTarget} \setminus (\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}} \cup \text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}})$ and that $F_2 = \text{coTarget} \setminus \text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$. We now invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2, F_3)$ in order to determine whether it holds that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 4} G) \leq 0.3$. In contrast to the previous example, this time we have to remove the set

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Exclude}^{\text{=3}} \\ &= \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 3/16 \cdot v[s_2] + 3/32 \cdot v[s_1] + 1/32 \cdot v[s_4] + 9/32 \cdot v[s_5] > 0.3\} \end{aligned}$$

from F_1 in order to exclude $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=2}}$ from F_2 .

Frames at the beginning of iteration 4:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_5} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_5 \doteq 1 \\ F_1 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ &\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.5 \\ &\quad \wedge 3/16 \cdot x_2 + 3/32 \cdot x_1 + 1/32 \cdot x_4 + 9/32 \cdot x_5 \leq 0.5 \\ F_2 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ &\quad \wedge 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot x_3 + 0.25 \cdot 0.25 \cdot x_2 + 0.75 \cdot 0.5 \cdot x_4 \leq 0.5 \\ F_3 &= x_I \leq 0.5 \wedge 0.25 \cdot x_1 + 0.75 \cdot x_2 \leq 0.5 \\ F_4 &= x_I \leq 0.5 . \end{aligned}$$

The goal of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4)$ is to determine whether $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 5} G) \leq 0.3$, which does not hold. This is established by $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ as follows: In order to remove $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=1}}$ from F_4 , we have to exclude the set

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Exclude}^{\text{=4}} \\ &= \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 5/128 \cdot v[s_2] + 3/128 \cdot v[s_3] + 3/32 \cdot v[s_4] + 19/64 \cdot v[s_5]\} \end{aligned}$$

from F_1 . For that, we test whether this violates relative inductiveness, i.e., whether it holds that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=4}} = \emptyset$. That is, for the 1-step reachability probabilities $v_1 = \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)$ it must hold that $v_1 \notin \text{Exclude}^{\text{=4}}$. Since $v_1[s_5] = 1$, $v_1[s_3] = v_1[s_4] = 1/2$, and $v_1[s] = 0$ for all $s \notin \{s_3, s_4, s_5\}$, we have

$$3/128 \cdot 1/2 + 3/32 \cdot 1/2 + 19/64 \cdot 1 = 97/256 \approx 0.3789 > 0.3 .$$

Hence, $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=4}}$ cannot be removed from F_1 and we have established that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > 0.3$. This yields $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ to soundly return **reachable** after 4 iterations. For other choices of λ , we have:

If $\lambda = 0.4$, then we need 6 iterations.

If $\lambda = 0.43$, then we need 11 iterations.

If $\lambda = 0.43334$, then we need 24 iterations. △

The reason why $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ determines whether $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$ holds is the following: If $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$, then there is an $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_0) > \lambda$. Eventually, the algorithm

needs to determine whether the set $\text{Exclude}^{\equiv i-1}$ can be removed from F_1 . For that, it checks whether this violates relative inductiveness, i.e., it checks whether it holds that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^{\equiv i-1} \neq \emptyset$. Since $F_0 = \{v_0\}$, this is equivalent to $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_0) > \lambda$ because

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^{\equiv i-1} \neq \emptyset \\ \text{iff} \quad & \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0) \in \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^{i-1}[s_I] > \lambda\} \\ & \quad \quad \quad (\text{Def. of } \Phi \text{ and } \text{Exclude}^{\equiv i-1}, F_0 = \{v_0\}) \\ \text{iff} \quad & \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

The respective invocation of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ thus returns $\text{flag} = \text{True}$, which yields $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ to return *reachable*. Intuitively speaking, the algorithm eventually finds a sufficient amount of paths from initial state s_I to a state in G such that the accumulated probabilities of these paths yield that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$.

On Generalization and Infinite Markov Chains. For a discussion on generalization in IC3 for Markov chains and on how to employ our concepts for model checking countably infinite Markov chains, we refer to Chapter 5.

4.2 Soundness and Termination

In this subsection, we prove $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ sound. Due to Theorem 3.18, it suffices to prove soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$. After that, we show that for $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$, termination of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ is guaranteed if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$. Finally, we provide an example where $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = \lambda$ holds and such that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ does *not* terminate.

In order to prove $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ sound, we employ the following auxiliary result for procedure $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$.

Lemma 4.9. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$ with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$, and let $i, k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \geq 1$. Furthermore, let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ be frames satisfying the IC3-Invariants. Finally, assume*

$$(\text{flag}, F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k) .$$

It holds:

1. *If Target is reachable in at most $i + k$ steps, i.e., if $\Phi^{i+k}(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, then:*
 - (a) $\text{flag} = \text{True}$.
2. *If Target is unreachable in at most $i + k$ steps, i.e., if $\Phi^{i+k}(I) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, then:*
 - (a) $\text{flag} = \text{False}$
 - (b) *The frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants.*
 - (c) $\Phi^i(F'_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$.
 - (d) *The frames are refined, i.e., $\forall 0 \leq j \leq k: F'_j \subseteq F_j$.*

Proof. For both cases, we proceed by induction on k .

Case 1: Target is reachable in at most $i + k$ steps.

Base case: $k = 1$. First, we show that the check in line 3 succeeds since

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i} \neq \emptyset \\
\text{iff } & \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0) \in \underbrace{\text{Exclude}^{=i}}_{=\{v \in [0,1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] > \lambda\}} \quad (F_0 = \{v_0\}) \\
\text{iff } & \Upsilon_{>0}^i(\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0))[s_I] > \lambda \quad (\text{Def. of } \text{Exclude}^{=i}) \\
\text{iff } & \Phi^{i+1}(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset. \quad (\text{Def. of } \Phi, \text{Target, and } I = \{v_0\})
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we invoke

$$(\text{flag}', F'_0) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i + 1, F_0),$$

which yields $\text{flag}' = \text{True}$ (lines 1–2). Consequently, for the top-level invocation of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ it holds that $\text{flag} = \text{True}$, which is what we had to show.

Induction hypothesis. Suppose that for some arbitrary, but fixed, $k \geq 1$ and all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ it holds that if $\Phi^{i+k}(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, then for

$$(\text{flag}', _) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

it holds that $\text{flag}' = \text{True}$.

Induction step. We have to show that if $\Phi^{i+k+1}(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$, then

$$(\text{flag}, _) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_{k+1})$$

yields $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Notice that $\Phi^{i+k+1}(I) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$ implies that $\Upsilon_{>0}^{i+k+1}(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda$. First, we show that the check in line 3 succeeds, i.e., we show that that $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i} \neq \emptyset$. Assume the contrary, i.e., assume that $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i} = \emptyset$. Since F_0, \dots, F_{k+1} satisfy the IC3-Invariants, we have $v_k \in F_k$, where $v_k \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ denotes the k -step reachability probabilities. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i} = \emptyset \\
\text{implies } & \Upsilon_{>0}(v_k) \notin \text{Exclude}^{=i} \quad (\text{Def. of } \Phi \text{ and } v_k \in F_k) \\
\text{implies } & \Upsilon_{>0}(\Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)) \notin \text{Exclude}^{=i} \quad (v_k = \Upsilon_{>0}^k(v_0)) \\
\text{implies } & \Upsilon_{>0}^{k+1}(v_0) \notin \text{Exclude}^{=i} \\
\text{implies } & \Upsilon_{>0}^{i+k+1}(v_0)[s_I] \leq \lambda,
\end{aligned}$$

which contradicts our assumption that $\Upsilon_{>0}^{i+k+1}(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda$. The above reasoning implies that we recursively invoke

$$(\text{flag}', _) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i + 1, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

in line 5. The induction hypothesis now implies that $\text{flag}' = \text{True}$. Finally, this yields the top-level invocation of $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ to return $\text{flag} = \text{True}$, which is what we had to show.

Case 2: Target is unreachable in at most $i + k$ steps.

Base case $k = 1$. First, we show that the check in line 3 fails, i.e., we show that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset \\ \text{iff} & \quad \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0) \notin \text{Exclude}^i && \text{(Def. of } \Phi \text{ and } F_0 = \{v_0\}) \\ \text{iff} & \quad \Upsilon_{>0}^{i+1}(v_0)[s_I] \leq \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

where the last statement holds by assumption. Hence, for the invocation of

$$(\text{flag}, F'_0, F'_1) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, F_1)$$

it holds that $\text{flag} = \text{False}$, $F'_0 = F_0$, and $F'_1 = F_1 \setminus \text{Exclude}^i$. Initiality, the chain-property, frame-safety, and the fact that the frames are refined are immediate. Since F_1 is inductive relative to F_0 , i.e., $\Phi(F_0) \subseteq F_1$ and since $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0) \notin \text{Exclude}^i$ (see above), it also holds that F'_1 is inductive relative to $F'_0 = F_0$. Finally, we have $\Phi^i(F'_1) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$ since

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi^i(F'_1) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset \\ \text{iff} & \quad \forall v \in F'_1: \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] \leq \lambda && \text{(Def. of } \Phi \text{ and Target)} \\ \text{iff} & \quad F'_1 \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

Induction hypothesis. Assume for an arbitrary, but fixed, $k \geq 1$ and all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ it holds that if $\Phi^{i+k}(I) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, then $\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ given by

$$(\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

satisfy Conditions (a)–(d) of Case 2.

Induction step. We have to show that if $\Phi^{i+k+1}(I) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, then $\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_{k+1}$ given by

$$(\text{flag}, F'_0, \dots, F'_{k+1}) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_{k+1})$$

satisfy Conditions (a)–(d) of Case 2. We distinguish the cases where the check in line 3 fails and where it succeeds.

Case $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset$. We have $F'_j = F_j \setminus \text{Exclude}^i$ for all $1 \leq j \leq k + 1$ and $\text{flag} = \text{False}$ (lines 8–9). Thus, initiality, frame-safety, and the chain-property are immediate. It remains to show that $\Phi(F'_j) \subseteq F'_{j+1}$ for all $1 \leq j < k + 1$ (relative inductiveness). Since $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset$ and since $\Phi(F_k) \subseteq F_{k+1}$, we have $\Phi(F'_k) \subseteq F'_{k+1}$. Now suppose that there is a $1 \leq j < k$ with $\Phi(F'_j) \not\subseteq \Phi(F'_{j+1})$. Since $\Phi(F_j) \subseteq \Phi(F_{j+1})$, there is a $v \in F'_j$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \text{Exclude}^i$. Due to the chain-property, this implies that $v \in F'_k$

and hence $\Phi(F'_k) \not\subseteq F'_{k+1}$, which is a contradiction.

Case $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} \neq \emptyset$. In this case, we recursively invoke

$$(\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i+1, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

The induction hypothesis yields that $\text{flag}' = \text{False}$, that $F''_k \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}} = \emptyset$, and that the frames F''_0, \dots, F''_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants and that they are refined. It remains to show that the frames F'_1, \dots, F'_{k+1} given by

$$F'_1 = F''_1 \setminus \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}}, \dots, F'_k = F''_k \setminus \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}}, F'_{k+1} = F_{k+1} \setminus \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}}$$

satisfy the IC3-Invariants. The fact that the frames are refined is immediate. Frame-safety and the chain-property are immediate. For relative inductiveness, consider the following: First, notice that $\Phi(F''_k) \subseteq F_{k+1}$ since $\Phi(F_k) \subseteq F_{k+1}$ and since $F''_k \subseteq F_k$. Furthermore, we have $F'_k \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}} = \emptyset$. Now suppose $\Phi(F'_k) \not\subseteq F'_{k+1}$. Then there is a $v \in F'_k$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}}$. This, however, implies that $v \in \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}}$, because we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} \\ \text{implies} & \quad \Upsilon_{>0}(v) \in \{v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} && \text{(Def. of Exclude}^{\text{=i}}\text{)} \\ \text{implies} & \quad v \in \{\Upsilon_{>0}(v') \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} \\ \text{implies} & \quad v \in \{v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^{i+1}(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} \\ \text{implies} & \quad v \in \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}}, && \text{Def. of Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}} \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction since $F'_k \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i+1}} = \emptyset$. Establishing that $\Phi(F'_j) \subseteq \Phi(F'_{j+1})$ for $0 < j < k$ is analogous to the previous case.

Finally, we show that $\Phi^i(F'_{k+1}) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$. Both of the preceding cases yield that $F'_{k+1} \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} = \emptyset$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi^i(F'_{k+1}) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset \\ \text{iff} & \quad \forall v \in F'_{k+1} : \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v)[s_I] \leq \lambda && \text{(Def. of } \Phi \text{ and Target)} \\ \text{iff} & \quad F'_{k+1} \cap \text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} = \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

We are now in a position to prove that $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound according to Definition 3.11.

Lemma 4.10. *Procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target}) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$. Furthermore, let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \geq 1$, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ be frames satisfying the IC3-Invariants. We have to show that for

$$(\text{flag}, F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

it holds that:

1. If Target is *reachable* in at most $k + 1$ steps, then:
 - (a) flag = True.
2. If Target is *not reachable* in at most $k + 1$ steps, then:
 - (a) flag = False.
 - (b) The frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants .
 - (c) The successors of locations in F'_k and Target are disjoint: $\Phi(F'_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$.
 - (d) The frames are refined: $\forall 0 \leq i \leq k: F'_i \subseteq F_i$.

Case 1: Target is reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps. First, notice that $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Target} \neq \emptyset$ since, otherwise, Target was not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps. Therefore, procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ invokes

$$(\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, \dots, F_k) .$$

According to Lemma 4.9, this invocation yields $\text{flag}' = \text{True}$. Hence, $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns $\text{flag} = \text{True}$ (lines 6–7).

Case 2: Target is not reachable in at most $k + 1$ steps. If the check in line 1 succeeds, i.e., if $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$, then $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ returns $(\text{True}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ and we have nothing to show (lines 1–2). Otherwise, we invoke

$$(\text{flag}', F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}] (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

such that Lemma 4.9 yields that $\text{flag}' = \text{False}$ and that F'_0, \dots, F'_k satisfy the conditions from above. This completes the proof. \square

Soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ now implies that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound.

Theorem 4.11 (Soundness of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$). *Procedure $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound.*

Proof. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound, Theorem 3.18 implies that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ is sound. \square

Let us now consider termination $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$. Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$. We show that termination is guaranteed if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$. If $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$, then Target is reachable by Lemma 4.2 such that Lemma 3.19 implies that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ terminates. For the case where $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) < \lambda$, we show that there is an i such that $\text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset$, which implies that eventually $F_1 = F_2$ holds.

Theorem 4.12. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$. If $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$, then $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ terminates.*

Proof. The case $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$ follows from Lemma 3.19 as described above. For the case where $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) < \lambda$ holds, consider the following. Let $v_{\top} \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $v_{\top}[s] = 1$ for all $s \in S_{>0}$. Since $\Upsilon_{>0}$ has a *unique* fixed-point, its least and the greatest fixed-point coincide, i.e.,

$$(\text{lfp } v. \Upsilon_{>0}(v)) [s_I] = \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = (\text{gfp } v. \Upsilon_{>0}(v)) [s_I] .$$

Figure 4.6: Markov chain \mathcal{C}_{rw} modeling a bounded random walk.

Let $v_{\top} \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $v_{\top}[s] = 1$ for all $s \in S_{>0}$. Hence, the Kleene Fixed-Point Theorem [LNS82] implies that

$$\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = \left(\inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Upsilon_{>0}^n(v_{\top}) \right) [s_I].$$

Since $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) < \lambda$, there is thus an $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_{\top})[s_I] < \lambda$. Hence, we have $\text{Exclude}^{\equiv i} = \emptyset$. To see this, notice that if $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v_{\top})[s_I] < \lambda$, then $\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v')[s_I] < \lambda$ for all $v' \leq v_{\top}$ (and thus for all $v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$). This yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Exclude}^{\equiv i} \\ &= \{v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^i(v')[s_I] > \lambda\} && \text{(Def. of Exclude}^{\equiv i}\text{)} \\ &= \emptyset. && (\Upsilon_{>0}^i(v')[s_I] < \lambda \text{ for all } v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}) \end{aligned}$$

In order to derive a contradiction, now suppose that $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ does *not* terminate. Since $\text{Strengthen}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ always terminates, $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ always reaches the next iteration. This implies that it eventually holds that

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\bigcup_{j=0}^i \text{Exclude}^{\equiv j} \right) \\ F_2 &= \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\bigcup_{j=0}^{i-1} \text{Exclude}^{\equiv j} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\text{Exclude}^{\equiv i} = \emptyset$, this implies that $F_1 = F_2$ such that $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ terminates, which contradicts our assumption. \square

If $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = \lambda$, then termination cannot be guaranteed in general. Hence, $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ is *not complete*. Our prototypical implementation of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ (cf. Section 4.3) underlines this: Consider the Markov chain \mathcal{C}_{rw} depicted in Figure 4.6 modeling a bounded random walk. The run of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}_{rw}, G, \lambda))$ with $G = \{s_4\}$ and $\lambda = \Pr^{\mathcal{C}_{rw}}(\diamond G)$ leads to a timeout ($> 1800\text{s}$) and does not produce a result.

```

dtmc
const int n = 5;
module bounded_random_walk
  x : [0..n] init 0;
  [] x = 0          → 0.5 : (x' = 1) + 0.5 : (x' = n);
  [] x > 0 & x < n - 1 → 0.5 : (x' = x - 1) + 0.5 : (x' = x + 1);
  [] x = n - 1     → 1 : (x' = n - 1);
  [] x = n         → 1 : (x' = n);
endmodule
label "goal" = x = n - 1;

```

Figure 4.7: A PRISM program.

4.3 Implementation and Experimental Evaluation

We have developed a prototypical implementation of algorithm IC3 $[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ in Python 3.7, which we present in this section. We present the architecture of our implementation as well as how SMT-techniques are employed in order to realize the necessary operations on the frames. After that, we evaluate some experimental results.

Our implementation supports the PRISM input language [pri]. This guarded command language offers a convenient way to build Markov chains. Consider the PRISM program depicted in Figure 4.7. It describes the Markov chain modeling the bounded random walk depicted in Figure 4.6 on page 60. The keyword `dtmc` declares that we describe a (discrete-time) Markov chain. After that, we declare a constant n and assign it the value 5. This feature allows us to use the same PRISM program for different instances of the described Markov chain. By choosing, e.g., $n = 100$, we obtain the bounded random walk where the goal state is 99 states apart from the initial state. Next, we declare the name of the module. It is possible to declare several modules which are then combined by parallel composition. Next, we declare a variable x whose domain are the integers ranging from 0 to n . Every state of the described Markov chain corresponds to one valuation of variable x . By `init 0`, we declare that the initial state of the Markov chain corresponds to the valuation that assigns value 0 to variable x . The subsequent commands determine the transition probability function of the Markov chain. For instance, the command

$$[] x = 0 \rightarrow 0.5 : (x' = 1) + 0.5 : (x' = n);$$

specifies that from state $x = 0$ we move to the successor state where $x = 1$ holds with probability 0.5 and that we fall down the cliff (state $x = n$) with probability 0.5. Similarly, the next command specifies that if x evaluates to a value in the integer interval $[1, n - 2]$, then we either decrement or increment x by one where both scenarios take place with

probability 0.5. Finally, the last command is used to specify the goal states. In general, we specify the goal states by the command

```
label "goal" = condition;
```

which says that every variable valuation satisfying `condition` corresponds to a goal state.

Since our algorithm $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ operates on explicitly represented Markov chains, we need to parse the PRISM program and to build the respective Markov chain. For that, we employ the Python bindings `StormPy` of the probabilistic model checker `Storm` [DJKV17]. These bindings provide access to the state space and the transition probability function of the described Markov chain. Furthermore, `StormPy` provides functions for obtaining the set $S_{>0}$ of states that reach a goal state specified by `condition` with a strictly positive probability. The architecture of our implementation is depicted in Figure 4.8 on page 63.

The core of the implementation is the realization of the necessary operations on the frames such as checking relative inductiveness. For that, we employ SMT solvers. SMT (shorthand for Satisfiability-Modulo-Theories) solvers such as `z3` [dMB08] or the solver `MathSAT` [CGSS13] are tools that provide methods for checking the satisfiability of logical formulae over certain background theories. $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ requires checking the satisfiability of formulae over the existential fragment of the theory of linear arithmetic over the reals (LRA, for short). For that, we employ the solver-agnostic Python library `PySMT` [GM15]. In what follows, we first describe the encoding of the frames and the respective operations. After that, we describe the realization in `PySMT`.

The check $\Phi(F_j) \cap \text{Exclude}^i = \emptyset$ is the core of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$. For that, we need to (1) encode the frames and (2) encode the reachability operator Φ (respectively the restricted reachability probability operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$). Consider $\text{MC } \mathcal{C}_{\text{rw}} = (S, s_I, P)$ with $G = \{s_4\}$ and $\lambda = 1/3$ depicted in Figure 4.6 on page 60 as a running example. For each state $s \in S_{>0}$, we assume two first order variables x_s and x'_s . Every frame is represented as a conjunction of constraints over the unprimed variables. For instance, after the initialization phase of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$, we have

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x_i \neq x_4} x_i \doteq 0 \wedge x_4 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 1/3.$$

By abuse of notation, we denote by F_i both the frame and the formula representing it. It remains to encode operator Φ . This is done by means of the constraint

$$\text{ReachOpConstraints} = \bigwedge_{x_i \in S_{>0}} (x'_i \doteq \sum_{s_j \in S_{>0}} P(s_i, s_j) \cdot x_j).$$

Now suppose we need to determine whether it holds that $\Phi(F_1) \cap \text{Exclude}^1 = \emptyset$. For that, we check the (un)satisfiability of the formula

$$\text{ProbabilityConstraints} \wedge \text{ReachOpConstraints} \wedge F_1 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x'_1 > 1/3, \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 4.8: Architecture of the Python implementation of IC3[[C_{>0}]].

where $\text{ProbabilityConstraints} = \bigwedge_{x_i} x_i \leq 1 \wedge \bigwedge_{x_i} x_i \geq 0$ asserts that every unprimed variable is bounded from above by 1 (resp. from below by 0). Formula 4.2 is unsatisfiable iff $\Phi(F_1) \cap \text{Exclude}^1 = \emptyset$. To see this, let $v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ (resp. $v' \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$) be a satisfying valuation of the unprimed (resp. primed) variables. Due to the constraints $\text{ProbabilityConstraints}$ and F_1 , this valuation is a model of Formula 4.2 only if $v \in F_1$. Furthermore, due to the conjunct $\text{ReachOpConstraints}$, we have $v'[s] = \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s]$. Hence, the fourth conjunct is satisfied iff $1/2 \cdot \Upsilon_{>0}(v)[s_1] > \lambda$, i.e., iff $v \in \text{Exclude}^1$. Formula 4.2 is therefore unsatisfiable iff no such v exists, which is the case iff $\Phi(F_1) \cap \text{Exclude}^1 = \emptyset$.

In general, for a check of the form $\Phi(F_j) \cap \text{Exclude}^i$, we check the satisfiability of the conjunction of $\text{ProbabilityConstraints}$, $\text{ReachOpConstraints}$, F_j , and the constraint corresponding to Exclude^i . Constraints $\text{ProbabilityConstraints}$ and $\text{ReachOpConstraints}$ are thus required for *every* satisfiability check in IC3[[C_{>0}]]. We can therefore make use of the incremental capabilities of PySMT. Access to the methods of the respective SMT solver is provided by an instance solver of the PySMT-class Solver. Object solver maintains a stack of *assertions*. An assertion is a formula over LRA. This stack is modified by means of three methods: `solver.push()`, `solver.add_assertion(assertion)`, and `solver.pop()`. Method `solver.push()` marks the current head of the stack. Method `solver.add_assertion(assertion)` pushes its argument onto the stack. Method `solver.pop()` removes assertions from the stack until it removes a marked assertion or—in case there is no marked assertion—until the stack is empty. Now suppose the stack consists of n assertions $[a_n, \dots, a_1]$,

where a_n is the head of the stack. By invoking `solver.solve()`, we check the satisfiability of the formula $\bigwedge_{i=1}^n a_i$. This formula is satisfiable iff `solver.solve()` returns True.

Before executing $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$, we set up the solver by pushing `ProbabilityConstraints` and `ReachOpConstraints` onto the solver stack. After that, we invoke `solver.push()` such that a subsequent call to `solver.pop()` removes all assertion from the stack except for `ProbabilityConstraints` and `ReachOpConstraints`. For a check of the form $\Phi(F_j) \cap \text{Exclude}^{=i}$, we then push frame F_j and the constraint corresponding to $\text{Exclude}^{=i}$ onto the stack. After checking for satisfiability, we call `solver.pop()` to remove these two constraints from the stack. The structure of the stack is depicted in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Structure of the solver stack.

Experimental Evaluation. We used our prototypical implementation to evaluate algorithm $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$. For that, we executed our algorithm on two benchmarks from the PRISM benchmark suite [KNP12]. More specifically, we used the two benchmarks `Crowds` and `BRP`. The results are shown in Tables 4.1–4.4. We briefly describe these benchmarks.

`Crowds` [Shm04] is an MC modeling a protocol for anonymizing the sender of a message in a network. Some of the members in the network try to determine the sender of that message. We are interested in the probability that the sender of the message is figured out by these members more than once. Parameter `CrowdSize` denotes the number of “good” members in the network, i.e., those members that do not try to figure out the sender of the message, and parameter `TotalRuns` determines the number of different paths through the network we aim to analyze.

`BRP` [DJJL01] is an MC modeling the bounded retransmission protocol. This protocol aims at sending a file which is subdivided into chunks, where the number of retransmissions of each chunk is bounded. Parameter N denotes the number of chunks to be sent and parameter `MAX` denotes the maximum number of retransmissions. When sending a chunk, there is a certain probability that this chunk is not transmitted successfully. We are interested in the probability that the file is not transmitted successfully, i.e., in the probability that the number of allowed retransmissions is exceeded for some chunk.

We ran our implementation of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ on these benchmarks with two different parameter instantiations each. The upper part of each table shows the results for those λ

λ	#Frames	Total Time	Solver Time	Frame Push Time
0.05	26	5.1	2.8	1.7
0.005	30	7.4	4.2	2.1
0.0005	32	9.9	6.2	2.3
0.00012	35	18.6	13.0	3.0
0.000104	31	12.5	7.5	2.5
0.00005	19	2.7	0.9	1.5
0.00003	14	0.7	0.2	0.4

Table 4.1: Results for BRP with $N = 4$ and $\text{Max} = 2$. We have $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) \approx 1.05e^{-4}$ and $|S_{>0}| = 162$.

for which $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) < \lambda$ holds and the lower part shows the results for instances with $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) > \lambda$. Column #Frames shows the number of frames needed upon termination. The next three columns denote different aspects of the computation time in seconds. Total Time denotes the total computation time, Solver Time denotes the computation time spent on checking the satisfiability of the assertions, and Frame Push Time is the amount of time needed to push the frames to the solver stack, i.e., constructing the assertions. We started measuring time *after* pushing the encoding of $\Upsilon_{>0}$ onto the solver stack. Every benchmark clearly shows that the smaller the difference between λ and the actual reachability probability $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G)$, the more computation time we need. This is due to the fact that the algorithm needs to discover an increasing amount of paths to a goal state (respectively to states in $S_{=0}$) to establish that $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) > \lambda$ (respectively $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) < \lambda$). For instance, consider the Crowds benchmark shown in Table 4.4. For $\lambda = 0.8 \gg \text{Pr}^c(\diamond G)$, our tool needs 3.4 seconds to find an inductive strengthening. In contrast, for $\lambda = 0.15$, our tool needs 538.7 seconds to find an inductive strengthening. For the cases where $\text{Pr}^c(\diamond G) > \lambda$, the situation is analogous: For $\lambda = 0.01 \ll \text{Pr}^c(\diamond G)$, our tool needs 1.2 seconds to terminate whereas for $\lambda = 0.1$, our tool reports a timeout ($> 1800s$) even though $S_{>0}$ is relatively small (100 states). Furthermore, we see that most of the computation time is spent on calls to the SMT solver. This reflects that the check $\Phi(F_{k-1}) \cap \text{Exclude}^{-i}$ (line 3 of procedure `BlockLocationsInFrame[[$\mathcal{C}_{>0}$]]`) is the core of `IC3[[$\mathcal{C}_{>0}$]]`. Nevertheless, the time needed to push the frames onto the solver stack is not negligible. In the third row of Table 4.2, about 9.7% of the total computation time is spent on pushing the frames onto the solver stack.

Our tool can handle MCs with a few hundred states and suitable choices of λ . For larger MCs, however, our tool mostly reports a timeout. This is not surprising: Recall standard backward IC3 from Chapter 3.4. We have seen that standard backward IC3 *without generalization* actually performs a (forward) breadth-first search from the initial locations until it either finds an inductive strengthening of `coTarget` or a path from an initial location to a `Target` location. In fact, proceeding in this incremental fashion without generalization actually creates an overhead. Performing the breadth-first search without starting all over from frame F_k on each new main iteration is obviously more efficient

λ	#Frames	Total Time	Solver Time	Frame Push Time
0.05	50	135.0	120.0	12.6
0.005	54	139.6	120.5	12.6
0.0005	56	149.3	124.9	14.3
0.000211	59	396.8	350.2	18.4
0.0002	53	93.5	75.2	13.1
0.00015	42	30.5	21.8	6.2
0.0001	31	9.3	5.1	3.1

Table 4.2: Results for BRP with $N = 8$ and $\text{Max} = 2$. We have $\Pr^C(\diamond G) \approx 2.12e^{-4}$ and $|S_{>0}| = 330$.

than performing the breadth-first search using the frames. Proceeding in this incremental fashion is necessary only in the presence of generalization. Furthermore, in efficient implementations of IC3 [EMB11] (which is called *PDR* in this paper), 80% of the computation time is spent on generalization on average. This underlines that generalization is *the* ingredient that yields IC3 to be efficient. The preceding arguments also hold for $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$. Proceeding incrementally without generalization creates the same overhead as in standard (backward) IC3 without generalization. One can show that it will always be frame F_1 that serves as an inductive strengthening. The situation is thus similar to standard backward IC3. Instead of starting all over from frame F_k on each iteration, we could just keep removing the sets Exclude^i from frame F_1 for increasing $i = 1, 2, \dots$ and test whether this would violate relative inductiveness w.r.t. F_0 . After each iteration, we test whether F_1 is an inductive strengthening, i.e., whether it holds that $\Phi(F_1) \subseteq F_1$. This results in a sound algorithm which terminates iff $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ terminates. Furthermore, it is important to note that SMT solvers use *exact* arithmetic instead of floating-point arithmetic, which has a significant impact on the performance.

The efficiency of Bradley’s (symbolic) IC3 clearly stems from the fact that it is suitable to work directly on the *symbolically* represented transition system and that this symbolic representation can be exploited to obtain generalizations. Hence, after investigating how the fundamental concepts of IC3 can be employed for model checking Markov chains, it might be worthwhile to investigate how to employ IC3 on—in some sense—*symbolically* represented Markov chains. As it is the case for Bradley’s symbolic version of IC3, this enables generalization. We refer to Chapter 5 where we discuss ideas on generalization.

λ	#frames	Total Time	Solver Time	Frame Push Time
0.8	18	3.4	1.6	1.4
0.4	30	16.3	11.8	2.8
0.2	42	112.3	105.7	5.6
0.15	52	538.7	477.5	9.8
0.1	-	TO	TO	TO
0.08	38	48.6	39.3	4.2
0.05	26	4.7	2.8	1.3
0.01	13	1.2	0.3	0.8

Table 4.3: Results for Crowds with TotalRuns = 3 and CrowdSize = 2. We have $\Pr^c(\diamond G) \approx 0.116$ and $|S_{>0}| = 100$.

λ	#frames	Total Time	Solver Time	Frame Push Time
0.8	18	5.2	2.5	2.6
0.4	27	37.9	29.7	4.8
0.2	31	76.5	63.8	6.3
0.15	34	145.9	125.6	8.2
0.05	-	TO	TO	TO
0.03	26	22.1	13.2	6
0.2	20	7.7	3.4	3.5
0.01	13	3.2	0.9	2.1

Table 4.4: Results for Crowds with TotalRuns = 3 and CrowdSize = 5. We have $\Pr^c(\diamond G) \approx 0.053$ and $|S_{>0}| = 331$.

4.4 On-The-Fly Computation of $S_{=0}$

In Section 4.1, we assumed that we have the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with a strictly positive probability at hand and defined the transition system underlying $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$ by means of the *restricted* reachability operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$. We have seen that knowing the set $S_{=0}$ is essential for establishing that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) < \lambda$ holds.

In this section, we present an extension of IC3 for finite Markov chains that allows to drop both the assumption of knowing $S_{=0}$ upfront and the requirement that $s_I \in S_{=0}$. The idea is to compute (sufficient subsets of) the set $S_{=0}$ on-the-fly while searching for an inductive strengthening. We extend algorithm $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ by an incremental, *qualitative* reachability analysis. This might be particularly useful if the Markov chain under consideration is too large such that computing the set $S_{=0}$ upfront is infeasible.

Assumptions. We assume a finite Markov chain $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$. Furthermore, given $G \subseteq S$, we assume that all states $s \in G$ are *absorbing*.

Our goal is to extend $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ to obtain an algorithm for the following problem:

Given a finite Markov chain $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$, a set of goal states G ,
and a rational threshold $\lambda \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$, determine whether $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$.

Notice that we are now allowed to choose $\lambda = 0$ since it is possible that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = 0$ holds. As in Section 4.1, we first provide a translation from the above problem to a reachability problems of an infinite transition system.

Definition 4.13 (Reachability Problem induced by MC \mathcal{C} , G , and λ). *Let \mathcal{C} be an MC, $G \subseteq S$, and let $\lambda \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$. The reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$ induced by \mathcal{C} , G , and λ is defined as*

$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) = (\text{TS}, \text{Target})$, where:

1. $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$ is an infinite transition system, where:

(a) The set of locations is the set of all assignments from states in S to probabilities, i.e.,

$$L = [0, 1]^S.$$

(b) The set of initial locations is the singleton $I = \{v_0\}$, where

$$v_0[s] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in G \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(c) The successor function Succ is induced by Υ , i.e., $\text{Succ}(v) = \{\Upsilon(v)\}$.

2. Target is the set of all locations v with $v[s_I] > \lambda$, i.e.,

$$\text{Target} = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid v[s_I] > \lambda\}.$$

Notice that coTarget is the set of all locations v with $v[s_I] \leq \lambda$, i.e.,

$$\text{coTarget} = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid v[s_I] \leq \lambda\}.$$

Finally, we denote by

$$\mathfrak{C} = \{ \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \mid \mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P) \text{ is an MC, } G \subseteq S, \text{ and } \lambda \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}} \}$$

the class of reachability problems induced by finite MCs. \triangle

Algorithm 7: IC3 $[\mathfrak{C}]$ ($\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$)

Data: A reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}$.

Result: According to Definition 3.7.

```

1 if  $v_0[s_I] > \lambda$  or  $\Upsilon(v_0)[s_I] > \lambda$  then
2   | return reachable;
3  $F_0 \leftarrow \{v_0\}$ ;
4  $F_1 \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
5  $k \leftarrow 1$ ;
6 while True do
7   |  $(\text{flag}, F'_0, \dots, F'_k) \leftarrow$ 
8     |  $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, \dots, F_k)$ ;
9     | if flag then
10    | | return reachable;
11    |  $F_0, \dots, F_k \leftarrow F'_0, \dots, F'_k$ ;
12    |  $F_{k+1} \leftarrow \text{coTarget}$ ;
13    |  $k \leftarrow k + 1$ ;
14    | if  $\exists 0 \leq i < k: F_i = F_{i+1}$  then
15    | | return unreachable;
16 end

```

Figure 4.10: (The extended version of) IC3 for finite Markov chains. Here Υ denotes the reachability probability operator determined by the underlying MC \mathcal{C} and the set of goal states G .

Definition 4.13 differs from Definition 4.1 in two aspects. First, the set of locations L as well as Target and coTarget, respectively, are defined over the whole state space S instead of $S_{>0}$. Second, instead of employing the *restricted* reachability probability operator $\Upsilon_{>0}$, we employ the reachability probability operator Υ in order to define the successor function. Proving the translation sound is completely analogous to the proof of Lemma 4.2.

Lemma 4.14. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}$. We have that Target is unreachable iff $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$.*

Proof. Analogous to the proof of Lemma 4.2. \square

We now develop IC3 $[\mathfrak{C}]$ by providing an implementation of Strengthen $[\mathfrak{C}]$. As it is the case for IC3 $[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, given k frames F_0, \dots, F_k , every frame F_i computed by IC3 $[\mathfrak{C}]$ over-approximates the reachability probabilities for up to i steps, i.e.,

$$F_i \supseteq \{ \Upsilon^j(v_0) \mid 0 \leq j \leq i \} \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq i \leq k.$$

Algorithm 8: Strengthen $\llbracket\mathcal{C}\rrbracket(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, \dots, F_k)$

```

1  $(F_0, \dots, F_k) \leftarrow \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 0, F_0, \dots, F_k);$ 
2 if  $\Phi(F_k) \cap \text{Target} = \emptyset$  then
3   | return  $(\text{False}, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ 
4  $(\text{flag}, F_0, \dots, F_k) \leftarrow$ 
5    $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}\llbracket\mathcal{C}\rrbracket(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, \dots, F_k);$ 
6 if flag then
7   | return  $(\text{True}, \_);$ 
8 return  $(\text{False}, F_0, \dots, F_k);$ 

```

Algorithm 9: Prob0States $(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k)$

Data:

1. A reachability problem $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}_{>0}$ with $\text{TS} = (L, I, \text{Succ})$.
2. A natural number $i \in \mathbb{N}$.
3. Frames F_0, \dots, F_k satisfying the IC3-Invariants.

Result: According to Lemma 4.18 and Lemma 4.20.

```

1 if  $k = 0$  then
2   | return  $F_0;$ 
3  $(F_0, \dots, F_{k-1}) \leftarrow \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i + 1, F_0, \dots, F_{k-1});$ 
4 for  $s \in \text{ReachStates}^i$  do
5   | if  $\Phi(F_{k-1}) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$  then
6     | |  $F_1, \dots, F_k \leftarrow F_1 \setminus \text{Positive}(s), \dots, F_k \setminus \text{Positive}(s);$ 
7 end
8 return  $(F_0, \dots, F_k);$ 

```

Figure 4.11: Implementation of procedure Strengthen $\llbracket\mathcal{C}\rrbracket$ for finite Markov chains. Here Υ denotes the reachability probability operator of \mathcal{C} and G . Φ denotes the reachability operator induced by TS.

The difference is that the frames now include the reachability probabilities for *all* $s \in S$ since we employ Υ instead of $\Upsilon_{>0}$. Fix an MC \mathcal{C} , a set of goal states G , and $\lambda \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$. By abuse of notation, we now denote by $\text{ReachStates}^{\text{=i}}$ all states $s \in S$ that are reachable from s_I in *exactly* i steps. Furthermore, we now define the Exclude sets as follows:

Definition 4.15 (Exclude sets). *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}$, and let $i \in \mathbb{N}$. The set $\text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} \subseteq [0, 1]^S$ (w.r.t. $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$) is defined as*

$$\text{Exclude}^{\text{=i}} = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \Upsilon^i(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} . \quad \triangle$$

Finally, for each $s \in S$, we define the set $\text{Positive}(s)$ of reachability probabilities indicating that the probability to reach a state in G from state s is greater than 0.

Definition 4.16 (Positive sets). *Let $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ be an MC. For each $s \in S$, the set $\text{Positive}(s) \subseteq [0, 1]^S$ is defined as*

$$\text{Positive}(s) = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid v[s] > 0\} . \quad \triangle$$

Algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}]$ is depicted in Figure 4.10 on page 69. Analogously to $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, we first check whether the probability to reach a state in G from initial state s_I in zero or one steps exceeds the threshold λ already. As usual in IC3, the core of the algorithm is procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}]$ depicted in Figure 4.11 on page 70. We omit procedure $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}]$ as it coincides with $\text{BlockLocationsInFrame}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$. Now observe that procedure $\text{Strengthen}[\mathfrak{C}]$ is extended by the call to procedure Prob0States in line 1. This procedure is responsible for the on-the-fly computation of (subsets of) $S_{=0}$. An invocation of the form

$$\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

determines for which states $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\text{=i}}$ reachable in exactly i steps it holds that the probability $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G)$ to reach a state in G from s in at most k steps is 0. For every such state s , it subsequently removes the set $\text{Positive}(s)$ from F_k . For that, Prob0States proceeds recursively. Recall that probability $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G)$ is given by the probabilities $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s' \models \diamond^{\leq k-1} G)$ of all *direct* successors s' of s . We have

$$\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G) = 0 \quad \text{iff} \quad \text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s' \models \diamond^{\leq k-1} G) = 0 \text{ for all direct successors } s' \text{ of } s .$$

Therefore, we recursively invoke $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i+1, F_0, \dots, F_{k-1})$ to determine for which direct successors s' of s the above statement holds. After that, we iterate over each $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\text{=i}}$ and test whether it holds that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq k} G) = 0$ (line 5). This is done by the check $\Phi(F_{k-1}) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$ because we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(F_{k-1}) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v' \in F_{k-1}: \Upsilon(v') \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset && \text{(Def. of } \Phi) \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v' \in F_{k-1}: \Upsilon(v') \cap \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid v[s] > 0\} = \emptyset && \text{(Def. of } \text{Positive}(s)) \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v' \in F_{k-1}: \Upsilon(v')[s] = 0 && (v[s] \leq 0 \text{ iff } v[s] = 0) \\ \text{iff} \quad & \forall v' \in F_{k-1}: \sum_{s' \in S} P(s, s') \cdot v[s'] = 0 && \text{(Def. of } \Upsilon) \end{aligned}$$

iff $\forall v' \in F_{k-1}: \forall \text{ direct successors } s' \text{ of } s: v'[s'] = 0.$

Hence, if $v'[s'] = 0$ for all $v' \in F_{k-1}$ (i.e. if $F_{k-1} \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$) and all direct successors s' of s , we can soundly remove all locations v from frame F_k with $v[s] > 0$ without violating the IC3-Invariants.

Remark. We remove the set $\text{Positive}(s)$ from F_1, \dots, F_{k-1} only for the sake of modular soundness proofs. When implementing procedure `Prob0States`, it suffices to remove the set $\text{Positive}(s)$ from F_k since it has been removed from F_1, \dots, F_{k-1} in the preceding iterations.

Figure 4.12: An MC $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ with the set of goal states $G = \{s_3, s_7\}$.

Let us consider an example run of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C} \rrbracket]$.

Example 4.17. Consider the MC \mathcal{C} and the set of goal states $G = \{s_4, s_8\}$ depicted in Figure 4.12. We have $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) = 5/16$. Notice that $S_{=0} = \{s_2, s_6\}$. We start the run of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ with $\lambda = 3/4$.

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 1:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x \notin \{x_3, x_7\}} x \doteq 0 \wedge x_3 \doteq 1 \wedge x_7 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 3/4.$$

We now invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\llbracket \mathcal{C} \rrbracket](\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1)$. The subsequent call to $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}, F_0, F_1)$ removes $\text{Positive}(s_I)$ from F_1 since $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) = 0$. Next, we remove Exclude^1 from F_1 . After initializing a new frame F_2 , we have:

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 2:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x \notin \{x_3, x_7\}} x \doteq 0 \wedge x_3 \doteq 1 \wedge x_7 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_I \doteq 0$$

$$F_2 = x_I \leq 3/4.$$

Observe that F_1 reflects that $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) = 0$. This implies that F_1 can not serve as an inductive strengthening of coTarget because such an inductive strengthening contains all actual reachability probabilities. Since $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond G) \neq 0$, frame F_1 cannot satisfy this condition.

Next, we invoke $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), F_0, F_1, F_2)$. In order to determine whether it holds that $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 2} G) = 0$, we call $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 0, F_0, F_1, F_2)$. For that, in turn, we recursively invoke $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), 1, F_0, F_1)$. Since $\Pr^C(s_2 \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) = 0$ and $\Pr^C(s_1 \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) \neq 0$, we remove $\text{Positive}(s_2)$ from F_1 . Furthermore, this yields $\Pr^C(s_I \models \diamond^{\leq 2} G) \neq 0$ such that we do not remove $\text{Positive}(s_2)$ from F_2 . Procedure Prob0States terminates and we remove $\text{Exclude}^{\leq 2}$ from F_1 and $\text{Exclude}^{\leq 1}$ from F_2 . We now initialize a new frame F_3 :

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 3:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x \notin \{x_3, x_7\}} x \doteq 0 \wedge x_3 \doteq 1 \wedge x_7 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_I \doteq 0$$

$$\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0$$

$$F_2 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4$$

$$F_3 = x_I \leq 3/4.$$

We skip the details of the next iterations and depict the resulting frames instead.

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 4:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x \notin \{x_3, x_7\}} x \doteq 0 \wedge x_3 \doteq 1 \wedge x_7 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_I \doteq 0$$

$$\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0$$

$$F_2 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4$$

$$\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0$$

$$F_3 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4$$

$$F_4 = x_I \leq 3/4.$$

The next iteration leads to an inductive strengthening of coTarget :

Frames at the beginning of main iteration 5:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x \notin \{x_3, x_7\}} x \doteq 0 \wedge x_3 \doteq 1 \wedge x_7 \doteq 1$$

$$F_1 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_I \doteq 0$$

$$\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0$$

$$F_2 = x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4$$

$$\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_3 &= x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \\
&\quad \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_2 + 1/4 \cdot x_3 + 1/4 \cdot x_4 \leq 3/4 \wedge x_2 \doteq 0 \\
F_4 &= x_I \leq 3/4 \wedge 1/2 \cdot x_1 + 1/2 \cdot x_2 \leq 3/4 \\
F_5 &= x_I \leq 3/4.
\end{aligned}$$

Since $F_2 = F_3$, procedure $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$ terminates and returns *unreachable*. Notice that it suffices to discover the proper subset $\{s_2\}$ of $S_{>0}$ in order to find an inductive strengthening. The fact that we have to compute (subsets of) $S_{>0}$ on-the-fly yields that procedure $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$ needs more iterations than $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$. For this example, $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ terminates after two iterations. \triangle

Soundness and Termination. In order to prove $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$ sound, it suffices to show that every call to procedure Prob0States terminates and maintains the IC3-Invariants. Soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}]$ is then implied by soundness of $\text{Strengthen}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$.

Lemma 4.18 (Soundness of Prob0States). *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathcal{C}$, let $k, i \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq [0, 1]^S$ be frames satisfying the IC3-Invariants. Furthermore, assume that*

$$(F'_0, \dots, F'_k) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k).$$

We have:

1. The call to $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_k)$ terminates.
2. The frames F'_0, \dots, F'_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants.
3. The frames are refined, i.e., $\forall 0 \leq j \leq k: F'_j \subseteq F_j$.

Proof. By induction on k .

Base case $k = 0$. Immediate since $F'_0 = F_0$.

Induction hypothesis. Assume the lemma holds for some arbitrary, but fixed, $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Induction step. We have to show that the invocation

$$(F'_0, \dots, F'_{k+1}) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i, F_0, \dots, F_{k+1})$$

terminates and that the frames F'_0, \dots, F'_{k+1} satisfy the IC3-Invariants and that they are refined. The induction hypothesis implies that the recursive invocation

$$(F''_0, \dots, F''_k) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), i+1, F_0, \dots, F_k)$$

in line 3 terminates, that the frames F''_0, \dots, F''_k satisfy the IC3-Invariants, and that they are refined. The for loop beginning in line 4 terminates since ReachStates^i is finite. Next, we show that the IC3-Invariants hold at the beginning of that loop and that each iteration preserves them.

The IC3-Invariants hold at the beginning of the loop. Since F_0, \dots, F_{k+1} satisfy the IC3-Invariants and since $F''_j \subseteq F_j$ for all $0 \leq j \leq k$, the frames F'_0, \dots, F'_{k+1} satisfy the

IC3-Invariants, too.

The loop preserves the IC3-Invariants. Denote by $\tilde{F}_0, \dots, \tilde{F}_{k+1}$ the frames at the beginning of the loop. These frames are assumed to satisfy the IC3-Invariants. We show that the frames $\tilde{F}'_0, \dots, \tilde{F}'_{k+1}$ resulting from one iteration satisfy the IC3-Invariants, too. Let $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\bar{i}}$. If $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_k) \cap \text{Positive}(s) \neq \emptyset$, then we have nothing to show. Now suppose that $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_k) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$. This yields that

$$\tilde{F}'_0 = \tilde{F}_0, \tilde{F}'_1 = \tilde{F}_1 \setminus \text{Positive}(s), \dots, \tilde{F}'_{k+1} = \tilde{F}_{k+1} \setminus \text{Positive}(s).$$

Initiality, frame-safety, and the chain-property are immediate. For relative inductiveness, consider the following: Since $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_k) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$ and since $\Phi(\tilde{F}_k) \subseteq \tilde{F}_{k+1}$, we have $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_k) \subseteq \tilde{F}'_{k+1}$. It remains to show that $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_j) \subseteq \tilde{F}'_{j+1}$ for $0 < j < k$. Assume the contrary, i.e., assume that $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_j) \not\subseteq \tilde{F}'_{j+1}$ for some $0 < j < k$. Since $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_j) \subseteq \tilde{F}_{j+1}$, this implies that there is a $v \in \tilde{F}'_j$ with $\Upsilon(v) \in \text{Positive}(s)$. The chain-property yields that $v \in \tilde{F}'_k$ and thus $\Phi(\tilde{F}'_k) \not\subseteq \tilde{F}'_{k+1}$, which is a contradiction.

Furthermore, every iteration of the loop obviously refines the frames, which yields that $F'_j \subseteq F_j$ for all $0 \leq j \leq k+1$. □

Theorem 4.19 (Soundness of IC3[[\mathcal{C}]]). *Procedure IC3[[\mathcal{C}]] is sound.*

Proof. Since procedure Prob0States preserves the IC3-Invariants, terminates, and refines the frames (Lemma 4.18), proving Strengthen[[\mathcal{C}]] sound is completely analogous to proving Strengthen[[$\mathcal{C}_{>0}$]] sound. Hence, Theorem 3.18 implies that IC3[[\mathcal{C}]] is sound. □

Let us now consider termination of IC3[[\mathcal{C}]]. Similar to IC3[[$\mathcal{C}_{>0}$]], we obtain that termination of IC3[[\mathcal{C}]]($\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda)$) is guaranteed if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$. First, we prove an auxiliary result for procedure Prob0States. Let \mathcal{C} be an MC. Given a frame $F \subseteq [0, 1]^S$, we denote by $\text{Prob0}(F) = \{s \in S \mid \forall v \in F: v[s] = 0\}$ the set of states s with $F \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$.

Lemma 4.20. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathcal{C}$, let $k \geq 1$, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \in [0, 1]^S$ be frames. If*

$$(F'_0, \dots, F'_j) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k-j, F_0, \dots, F_j),$$

then

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\bar{i}}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F'_j)),$$

for all $0 < j \leq k$.

Proof. By induction on j .

Base case $j = 1$. Let

$$(F'_0, F'_1) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k-1, F_0, F_1).$$

The subsequent call to $\text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k, F_0)$ has no effect. Furthermore, since $\Phi(F_0) = \{\Upsilon(v_0)\}$, we have $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$ iff $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq 1} G) = 0$ for all

$s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-1}$, which implies the desired result.

Induction hypothesis. Assume for some arbitrary, but fixed, $j \geq 1$ it holds that if

$$(F'_0, \dots, F'_j) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k-j, F_0, \dots, F_j),$$

then we have

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-j}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F'_j)).$$

Induction step. We have to show that if

$$(F'_0, \dots, F'_{j+1}) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k-j-1, F_0, \dots, F_{j+1}),$$

then we have

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-j-1}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j+1} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F'_{j+1})).$$

Now let

$$(F''_0, \dots, F''_j) = \text{Prob0States}(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda), k-j, F_0, \dots, F_j)$$

be the frames resulting from the recursive call in line 3. By I.H., we have

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-j}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F''_j)).$$

This yields that $\Phi(F''_j) \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-j-1}$ for which it holds that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j+1} G) = 0$. This implies that the **for** loop beginning in line 4 removes $\text{Positive}(s)$ from F_{j+1} for all these states s , which completes the proof. \square

Now denote by $\text{ReachStates}^{\leq k} = \bigcup_{i=0}^k \text{ReachStates}^{\leq i}$ the set of states reachable in at most k steps and suppose that $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ is about to perform main iteration k maintaining the frames F_0, \dots, F_k . Lemma 4.20 implies that

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq k-j-1}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq j} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F_j))$$

for all $0 < j < k$. Termination is implied by the fact that, for sufficiently large k , we eventually have two frames F_i, F_{i+1} with $\text{Prob0}(F_i) = \text{Prob0}(F_{i+1}) = S_{=0}$.

Lemma 4.21. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathcal{C}$ with $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$. Furthermore, let $k, i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k > i$, and let $F_0, \dots, F_k \subseteq [0, 1]^S$ be frames the frames at the beginning of main iteration k of $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$. If $k - i > |S|$ and $i > |S|$, then $\text{Prob0}(F_i) = \text{Prob0}(F_{i+1}) = S_{=0}$.*

Proof. For $\text{Prob0}(F_i), \text{Prob0}(F_{i+1}) \subseteq S_{=0}$, consider the following. Since $k - i > |S|$ and $i > |S|$, Lemma 4.20 implies that

$$\forall s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\leq |S|}: (\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq |S|} G) = 0 \text{ implies } s \in \text{Prob0}(F_j))$$

for $j \in \{i, i+1\}$. Furthermore, we have $\text{ReachStates}^{\leq |S|} = S$. Since for all $s \in S$ it holds that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(s \models \diamond^{\leq |S|} G) = 0$ iff $s \in S_{=0}$, we get $\text{Prob0}(F_i) \subseteq S_{=0}$ and $\text{Prob0}(F_{i+1}) \subseteq S_{=0}$.

For $S_{=0} \subseteq \text{Prob0}(F_i)$ and $S_{=0} \subseteq \text{Prob0}(F_{i+1})$, consider the following. Recall that, since

F_i and F_{i+1} satisfy the IC3-Invariants, we have $\Upsilon^i(v_0) \in F_i$ and $\Upsilon^{i+1}(v_0) \in F_{i+1}$. Furthermore, $i > |S|$ implies $\Upsilon^i(v_0)[s] > 0$ and $\Upsilon^{i+1}(v_0)[s] > 0$ for all $s \in S_{>0}$. In order to derive a contradiction, assume there is a state $s \in \text{Prob0}(F_i)$ with $s \notin S_{=0}$. This means that $v[s] = 0$ for all $v \in F_i$, which contradicts the fact that $\Upsilon^i(v_0) \in F_i$. The same argument holds for F_{i+1} . \square

Theorem 4.22. *Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}$. If $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$, then $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ terminates.*

Proof. If $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) > \lambda$, then termination is guaranteed by Theorem 3.19. Now assume that $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) < \lambda$. Furthermore, in order to derive a contradiction, assume that $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ does *not* terminate. Consider the frames F_0, \dots, F_k at the beginning of main iteration k for k sufficiently large. Due to Lemma 4.21, we have $\text{Prob0}(F_i) = \text{Prob0}(F_{i+1}) = S_{=0}$. Let $\text{Positive}(S_{=0}) = \bigcup_{s \in S_{=0}} \text{Positive}(s)$. Since $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}, G, \lambda))$ does not terminate, we have

$$F_i = \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\text{Positive}(S_{=0}) \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^h \text{Exclude}^{\neq j} \right)$$

$$\text{and } F_{i+1} = \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\text{Positive}(S_{=0}) \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^{h-1} \text{Exclude}^{\neq j} \right)$$

for some h . Notice that as k increases, so does h . For $v \in [0, 1]^S$, let $v_{>0} \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}}$ with $v_{>0}[s] = v[s]$ for all $s \in S_{>0}$. Now recall that $\Upsilon^h(v)[s_I]$ is the sum of the probabilities $p_s \cdot v[s]$ for all $s \in \text{ReachStates}^{\neq s}$, where p_s is the probability to move from state s_I to state s in exactly h steps. Hence, if frame F is of the form $F = F' \setminus \text{Positive}(S_{=0})$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & F \setminus \text{Exclude}^{\neq h} \\ &= F \setminus \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \Upsilon^h(v)[s_I] > \lambda\} \\ &= F \setminus \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \Upsilon^h(v)[s_I] > \lambda \wedge (v[s] = 0 \text{ for all } s \in S_{=0})\} \\ & \quad (F \cap \text{Positive}(s) = \emptyset \text{ for all } s \in S_{=0}) \\ &= F \setminus \underbrace{\{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \Upsilon_{>0}^h(v_{>0})[s_I] > \lambda \wedge (v[s] = 0 \text{ for all } s \in S_{=0})\}}_{=: E_h} \end{aligned}$$

In Theorem 4.12, we have seen that if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$, then $\Upsilon_{>0}^h(v_{>0})[s_I] \leq \lambda$ for sufficiently large h and thus $E_h = \emptyset$ for sufficiently large h . Finally, this yields

$$\begin{aligned} F_i &= \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\text{Positive}(S_{=0}) \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^h \text{Exclude}^{\neq j} \right) \\ &= \text{coTarget} \setminus \left(\text{Positive}(S_{=0}) \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^{h-1} \text{Exclude}^{\neq j} \right) = F_{i+1} \end{aligned}$$

for sufficiently large h and hence $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}]$ terminates, which contradicts our assumption. \square

Chapter 5

Future Work

We see several directions for future work. In what follows, we first point these directions out. Section 5.1 is dedicated to ideas and issues regarding generalization. In Section 5.2, we sketch how to employ our concepts for model checking countably infinite Markov chains. In particular, we consider Markov chains obtained from pPDAs.

Generalization. The next step in the development of IC3 for probabilistic systems is to investigate how to incorporate symbolic reasoning in order to obtain suitable generalizations. We refer to Section 5.1 where we discuss ideas on generalization and what issues we have to solve.

Infinite Systems. Even though we concentrated on finite Markov chains in this thesis, under certain circumstances, we can employ the algorithms developed in this thesis for model checking countably infinite Markov chains. We refer to Section 5.2 where we discuss these circumstances. Furthermore, we provide ideas on how to obtain generalizations for infinite Markov chains obtained from probabilistic pushdown automata.

Non-Deterministic Systems. Another direction for future work is to consider models that incorporate both probabilistic *and* non-deterministic behavior such as Markov decision processes (MDPs) [Put94]. The concepts developed in this thesis can be employed to obtain, e.g., an IC3-style algorithm for establishing upper bounds on maximal reachability probabilities in MDPs.

Rewards. In this thesis, we concentrated on reachability probabilities. Another interesting extension of IC3 for probabilistic systems is to consider expected rewards: Given a threshold $\theta \in \mathbb{Q}$, is the expected reward to eventually reach a set of goal states in a given reward Markov chain at most θ ? In contrast to reachability probabilities, expected rewards are not bounded by 1. Hence, we do not find an inductive strengthening until we have at least discovered all reachable states in the given Markov chain. Here we have to investigate in how far suitable techniques for obtaining generalizations can mitigate this.

Probabilistic Programs. Developing IC3 for probabilistic programs is a very interesting direction for future work. We believe that marrying the concepts developed in this thesis with the weakest preexpectation calculus by McIver & Morgan [MM05] might be a promising approach for achieving this. All of the aforementioned directions for future work play a role here. The operational semantics of a probabilistic program is given in terms of an *infinite* Markov chain [GKM14]. *Generalization* might be important for efficiency and feasibility. Furthermore, reasoning about, e.g., expected values of program variables requires reasoning about *expected rewards*.

5.1 Generalization

In this section, we consider a finite Markov chain obtained from a PRISM program and sketch how to obtain generalizations from this symbolic representation. Observe that the technique presented here is not meant as a final answer, but to illustrate how the idea behind generalization can be lifted to a probabilistic setting.

Consider the PRISM program P depicted in Figure 5.1 on page 81. The Markov chain $\mathcal{C}_P = (S, s_I, P)$ obtained from P with $n = 5$ is depicted in Figure 5.2 on page 82. Every state $\langle x, y \rangle$ corresponds to one valuation of the program variables. The initial state is given by $s_I = \langle 1, 2 \rangle$. Every state corresponding to a variable valuation where $x = 5$ holds is a goal state, i.e., $G = \{\langle x, y \rangle \in S \mid x = 5\}$. We depict reachable states only. The probability to eventually reach a goal state is given by $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}_P}(\diamond G) = 4/13$. We assume that we have the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with probability 0 at hand. The reachable states in $S_{=0}$ are given by $\{\langle x, y \rangle \mid y = 5\} \subseteq S_{=0}$.

We now consider the run of $\text{IC3}[\mathbb{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}_P, G, \lambda))$ with $\lambda = 5/13$. The algorithm needs 5 iterations in order to find an inductive strengthening proving that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}_P}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$ holds. By slight abuse of notation, we denote by F_i both the set of candidates for the i -step reachability probabilities and the formula representing it. After the initialization phase of $\text{IC3}[\mathbb{C}_{>0}]$, we have

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x=5} \langle x, y \rangle \doteq 1 \quad \wedge \quad \bigwedge_{x \neq 5} \langle x, y \rangle \doteq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_1 = \langle 1, 2 \rangle \leq 5/13 .$$

Next, we have to remove the set

$$\text{Exclude}^{\doteq 1} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 5, 2 \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot v[\langle 3, 1 \rangle] > 5/13\}$$

from F_1 . This corresponds to conjoining the constraint

$$0.25 \cdot \langle 5, 2 \rangle + 0.75 \cdot \langle 3, 1 \rangle \leq 5/13 , \tag{5.1}$$

to the respective formula. We thus refine the possible candidates of the 1-step reachability probabilities of states $\langle 5, 2 \rangle$ and $\langle 3, 1 \rangle$. The natural analog of generalization in IC3 for Markov chains is to restrict the candidates of the 1-step reachability probabilities of *more* states than those in $\text{ReachStates}^{\doteq 1}$. For that, we have to find a generalization Gen_1 with $\text{Exclude}^{\doteq 1} \subseteq \text{Gen}_1$ and need to check whether removing Gen_1 from F_1 violates relative inductiveness.

```

dtmc
const int n = 5;
module structured_mc
  x : [1..n] init 1;
  y : [1..n] init 2;
1 :   [] x = 1 & (y = n - 1)  → 0.25 : (x' = n) + 0.75 : (x' = 2) & (y' = 1);
2 :   [] x = 1 & (y! = n - 1) → 0.25 : (x' = n) + 0.75 : (x' = y + 1) & (y' = 1);

3 :   [] y = 1 & (x = n - 1)  → 0.75 : (y' = n) + 0.25 : (y' = 2) & (x' = 1);
4 :   [] y = 1 & (x! = n - 1) → 0.75 : (y' = n) + 0.25 : (y' = y + 1) & (x' = 1);

5 :   [] x = n                → 1 : (x' = x);
6 :   [] y = n                → 1 : (y' = x);
endmodule
label "goal" = x = n;

```

Figure 5.1: PRISM program P .

We proceed similar to Bradley’s IC3: We check whether “dropping” the fact that $y = 2$ holds in the first summand of Constraint 5.1 still yields a sound overapproximation of the 1-step reachability probabilities. Consider the set Gen_1 given by

$$\text{Gen}_1 = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S>0} \mid \forall y: 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 5, y \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot v[\langle 3, 1 \rangle] > 5/13\} .$$

By checking whether removing Gen_1 from F_1 violates relative inductiveness, we determine whether Constraint 5.1 does not only hold for state $\langle 5, 2 \rangle$, but for *all* states $\langle 5, y \rangle$ with $y \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ (depicted in red). For that, we need to check whether it holds that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset \\
\text{iff} & \quad \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0) \notin \text{Gen}_1 \\
\text{iff} & \quad \forall y \in \{1, \dots, 5\}: 0.25 \cdot \Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\langle 5, y \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot v_0[\langle 3, 1 \rangle] > 5/13 . \quad (5.2)
\end{aligned}$$

One possibility to determine whether Condition 5.2 holds is to enumerate the possible values for y . However, for larger instantiations of parameter n , this can be infeasible since, in general, we have $y \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Deriving whether Condition 5.2 holds in a symbolic manner is more desirable. From program P we derive that $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\langle 5, y \rangle] = v_0[\langle 5, y \rangle] = 1$ for all $y \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ (command 5). Since $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\langle 3, 1 \rangle] = 0$, this yields $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$ such that removing Gen_1 from F_1 does not violate relative inductiveness.

We can, however, generalize further. Consider the set $\text{Gen}_2 \supseteq \text{Gen}_1$ given by

$$\text{Gen}_2 = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S>0} \mid \forall y \forall x: 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 5, y \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot v[\langle x, 1 \rangle] > 5/13\} .$$

Figure 5.2: Reachable states of MC \mathcal{C}_P obtained from program P .

With this generalization, we additionally refine the candidates for the 1-step reachability probabilities of *all* blue states. Checking whether $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_2 = \emptyset$ holds requires to determine $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\langle x, 1 \rangle]$ for all $x \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$. Again, we derive these values from the underlying program P : $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\langle x, 1 \rangle]$ is determined by commands 3 and 4, respectively, for all $x \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$. We omit further details here. Since $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_2 = \emptyset$ holds, we finally remove Gen_2 from F_1 and obtain the following refined frames:

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{x=5} \langle x, y \rangle \doteq 1 \wedge \bigwedge_{x \neq 5} \langle x, y \rangle \doteq 0, \text{ and}$$

$$F_1 = \langle 1, 2 \rangle \leq 5/13 \wedge \bigwedge_y \bigwedge_x 0.25 \cdot \langle 5, y \rangle + 0.75 \cdot \langle x, 1 \rangle \leq 5/13$$

$$F_2 = \langle 1, 2 \rangle \leq 5/13$$

We have thereby not only refined the candidates of the 1-step reachability probabilities of states $\langle 1, 2 \rangle$ and $\langle 3, 1 \rangle$, but of *all* states $\langle 5, y \rangle$ and $\langle x, 1 \rangle$ with $y, x \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$.

In the next iteration, we have to remove the set

$$\text{Exclude}^{-2} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 5, 2 \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 1, 4 \rangle] > 5/13\}$$

from F_1 . Proceeding in a similar manner, we obtain the generalization

$$\text{Gen}_3 = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid \forall y \forall y' : 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 5, y \rangle] + 0.75 \cdot 0.25 \cdot v[\langle 1, y' \rangle] > 5/13\}$$

restricting the candidates of the 1-step reachability probabilities of *all* red and orange states. The test $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_3 = \emptyset$ succeeds such that we obtain a refinement of F_1 :

$$F_1 = \langle 1, 2 \rangle \leq 5/13 \wedge \bigwedge_y \bigwedge_x 0.25 \cdot \langle 5, y \rangle + 0.75 \cdot \langle x, 1 \rangle \leq 5/13$$

$$\wedge \bigwedge_y \bigwedge_{y'} 0.25 \cdot \langle 5, y \rangle + 0.75 \cdot 0.25 \cdot \langle 1, y' \rangle \leq 5/13$$

The next iteration will reveal that F_1 is an inductive strengthening and we terminate after 3 iterations. It is worthwhile to note that we find an inductive strengthening after 3 iterations for all $n > 5$ and all $\lambda = \Pr^{C^P}(\diamond G) + c$ with $c > 0$. Without generalization, the number of required iterations grows ad infinitum as n increases and c decreases.

The presented generalization technique is rather naive, but it demonstrates that generalization in IC3 for Markov chains is possible and might improve its efficiency drastically. We believe that it is worthwhile to investigate the presented technique as well as more sophisticated ones further. There are several directions for doing so. Implementation-wise, we have to investigate how to perform checks like $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$ *without* explicitly enumerating all possible values for y . As described above, we might exploit the symbolic representation of the Markov chain in form of the underlying program P to establish that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$ holds symbolically.

Furthermore, we assumed that we have pre-computed the set $S_{=0}$. For very large (or even unbounded, cf. Section 5.2) n , this can be infeasible. Here we can employ the extension $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$ of IC3 for Markov chains developed in Section 4.4. Developing a suitable generalization for the presented qualitative reachability analysis might obviate the need to pre-compute $S_{=0}$.

5.2 Infinite Systems

In Chapter 4, we assumed that all Markov chains are finite. However, we can employ algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ (respectively $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$) for model checking countably *infinite* Markov chains $\mathcal{C} = (S, s_I, P)$ while preserving soundness of the algorithm. For that, the respective sets Exclude^i must be computable for every $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Given a set of goal states $G \subseteq S$, we require an oracle for the following objects:

1. For every $s \in S$, we need an oracle for the direct successors s' of s and for the values $P(s, s')$ of the transition probability function.
2. For every $s \in S$, we need an oracle for deciding whether $s \in G$ holds.
3. Algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}_{>0}]$ requires an oracle for deciding whether $s \in S_{=0}$ holds. Algorithm $\text{IC3}[\mathcal{C}]$ does *not* require such an oracle.

In what follows, we provide two examples of countably infinite Markov chains obtained from (stateless) probabilistic pushdown automata (called probabilistic basic process algebra) to demonstrate under which condition our algorithm terminates. Furthermore, we provide ideas on how to obtain generalizations.

Definition 5.1 (pBPAs (adapted from [BEKK13])). A probabilistic basic process algebra (pBPA, for short) Δ is a triple

$$\Delta = (\Gamma, I, \hookrightarrow, \text{Prob}), \text{ where}$$

1. Γ is a finite stack alphabet,
2. $I \in \Gamma$ is the initial stack symbol,
3. $\hookrightarrow \subseteq \Gamma \times \Gamma^*$ is a finite set of rules such that for every $X \in \Gamma$ there is at least one rule of the form $X \hookrightarrow \alpha$, and
4. Prob is a probability assignment which to each rule $X \hookrightarrow \alpha$ assigns its probability $\text{Prob}(X \hookrightarrow \alpha) \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$ such that for all $X \in \Gamma$ it holds that $\sum_{X \hookrightarrow \alpha} \text{Prob}(X \hookrightarrow \alpha) = 1$.

Elements of Γ^* are called configurations. The empty configuration is denoted by $\epsilon \in \Gamma^*$. Given a configuration of the form $\beta = X\alpha$, we call X the head of configuration β . \triangle

A run of a pBPA $\Delta = (\Gamma, I, \hookrightarrow, \text{Prob})$ starts with the initial configuration I . The top-most entry X of the stack determines the distribution over the successor configurations. If the stack is empty, then we say that the pBPA has *terminated*. Otherwise, pBPA Δ pops the top-most entry X from the stack and for each rule of the form $X \hookrightarrow \alpha$, with probability $\text{Prob}(X \hookrightarrow \alpha)$, it pushes α onto the stack. Adapting the notation of [BEKK13], we write $X \xrightarrow{p} \alpha$ if $X \hookrightarrow \alpha$ and $\text{Prob}(X \hookrightarrow \alpha) = p$. If there is no rule of the form $X \hookrightarrow \alpha$, then we write $X \xrightarrow{0} \alpha$. A pBPA induces a countably infinite Markov chain.

Definition 5.2 (Markov chain induced by Δ). Let $\Delta = (\Gamma, I, \hookrightarrow, \text{Prob})$ be a pBPA. The (countably infinite) Markov chain \mathcal{C}_{Δ} induced by Δ is defined as

$$\mathcal{C}_{\Delta} = (S, s_I, P), \text{ where:}$$

1. The state space of \mathcal{C}_{Δ} is the set of configurations of Δ , i.e., $S = \Gamma^*$.
2. $s_I = I$.
3. The transition probability function P is defined defined as:

- (a) $P(\epsilon, \epsilon) = 1$, and
- (b) for all $\beta \in \Gamma^*$ we have $P(X\beta, \alpha\beta) = p$ iff $X \xrightarrow{p} \alpha$.

We call the states of \mathcal{C}_{Δ} configurations and denote them by Greek letters. \triangle

Given two configurations $\alpha, \alpha' \in S$, the value $P(\alpha, \alpha')$ is thus determined by the rules of Δ . We now consider two examples of pBPAs and the respective runs of $\text{IC3}[\llbracket \mathcal{C}_{>0} \rrbracket]$ on the induced Markov chain.

Figure 5.3: The Markov chain \mathcal{C}_Δ obtained from the pBPA Δ .

Example: Non-Termination. Consider the pBPA $\Delta = (\{I\}, I, \hookrightarrow, \text{Prob})$ with

$$I \xrightarrow{0.3} \epsilon \quad \text{and} \quad I \xrightarrow{0.7} II.$$

This pBPA is adapted from [KEM06] and models an unfair, one-sided bounded random walk. A reachable fragment of the respective Markov chain $\mathcal{C}_\Delta = (S, s_I, P)$ is depicted in Figure 5.3. Checking whether a given $\lambda \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{Q}}$ is an upper bound on the termination probability $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}_\Delta}(\diamond\epsilon)$ is known to be decidable by checking the satisfiability of a polynomial equation system [BEKK13, KEM06].

We have $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}_\Delta}(\diamond\epsilon) = 3/7$. Since $S_{=0} = \emptyset$ and $G = \{\epsilon\}$, it is decidable whether a given configuration $\alpha \in S$ belongs to one of these sets. This infinite Markov chain is an example where $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}_\Delta, G, \lambda))$ does *not* terminate for all $\lambda \in [3/7, 1)$, i.e., $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ cannot establish any non-trivial upper bound on the termination probability. We have seen in Chapter 4 and in particular in the proof of Theorem 4.12 that termination of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$ requires that there is a sufficient amount of finite paths that lead to a state in $S_{=0}$. This example demonstrates that, for infinite systems, this is not necessarily the case, even if $\text{Pr}^{\mathcal{C}_\Delta}(\diamond G) < \lambda$ holds.

Example: Termination. Consider the pBPA $\Delta_2 = (\{I, A, F, Z\}, I, \hookrightarrow, \text{Prob})$ with

$$\begin{array}{ll} I \xrightarrow{0.25} FI & I \xrightarrow{0.75} AI \\ A \xrightarrow{0.25} IA & A \xrightarrow{0.75} ZA \\ F \xrightarrow{1} F & Z \xrightarrow{1} Z. \end{array}$$

A reachable fragment of the respective MC $\mathcal{C}_{\Delta_2} = (S, s_I, P)$ is depicted in Figure 5.4 on page 86. It is the infinite version of the MC from the previous section. Let

$$G = \{\alpha \in S \mid F \text{ is the head of configuration } \alpha\}.$$

These configurations are depicted in red. Furthermore, the reachable configurations in $S_{=0}$ are a subset of $\{\alpha \in S \mid Z \text{ is the head of configuration } \alpha\} \subseteq S_{=0}$ (depicted in gray). It is thus decidable whether $\alpha \in G$ (respectively $\alpha \in S_{=0}$ for reachable α) holds by looking at the head of configuration α .

This infinite Markov chain is an example where $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}_{\Delta_2}, G, \lambda))$ terminates for all $\lambda \in (4/13, 1]$. This is due to the fact that for every such λ , it suffices to consider finitely many finite paths from configuration I to some configuration in $S_{=0}$. Now let

Figure 5.4: Markov chain \mathcal{C}_{Δ_2} obtained from pBPA Δ_2 .

$\lambda = \Pr^{\mathcal{C}_{\Delta_2}}(\diamond G) + c$ for some $c > 0$. If c tends to 0, the number of iterations required to establish that $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}_{\Delta_2}}(\diamond G) \leq \lambda$ tends to infinity since ever more paths to some configuration in $S_{=0}$ have to be discovered. We now discuss ideas on generalization for pBPAs.

We demonstrate a run of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}](\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{C}_{\Delta_2}, G, \lambda))$ with $\lambda = 5/13$. Given a configuration α , we denote by $\langle \alpha_- \rangle = \{\alpha\beta \mid \beta \in \Gamma^*\}$ the set of all configurations with prefix α . After the initialization phase of $\text{IC3}[\mathfrak{C}_{>0}]$, we have

$$F_0 = \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 1 \quad \wedge \quad \bigwedge_{\alpha \notin \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_1 = [I] \leq 5/13.$$

Next, we have to remove $\text{Exclude}^{\doteq 1} = \{v \in [0, 1]^{S_{>0}} \mid 0.25 \cdot v[FI] + 0.75 \cdot v[AI] > 5/13\}$ from F_1 . This corresponds to conjoining the constraint

$$0.25 \cdot [FI] + 0.75 \cdot [AI] \leq 5/13 \tag{5.3}$$

to the respective formula. In order to obtain a generalization, we proceed similar to Bradley's IC3: We do not only refine the candidates for the 1-step reachability probabilities of configuration FI (first summand of Constraint 5.3), but of all configurations with prefix F (depicted in red). We thus obtain the generalization

$$\text{Gen}_1 = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \forall \alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle: 0.25 \cdot v[\alpha] + 0.75 \cdot v[AI] > 5/13\}$$

and need to check whether $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$ holds.

In this infinite-state setup, it is not possible to enumerate all $\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle$, i.e., we rely on symbolic methods for this check. From the rule $F \xrightarrow{1} F$ we derive that whenever the

top-most stack entry is an F , then with probability 1 there is again an F on top of the stack. From that, we get for all $\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle$ that $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\alpha] = v_0[\beta]$ for some $\beta \in \langle F_- \rangle$. Since $v_0[\beta] = 1$ for all $\beta \in \langle F_- \rangle$, this yields $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\alpha] = 1$ for all $\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle$. Hence, we derive that $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_1 = \emptyset$ holds.

Before we remove Gen_1 from F_1 , we try to generalize further. Consider the set $\text{Gen}_2 \supseteq \text{Gen}_1$ given by

$$\text{Gen}_2 = \{v \in [0, 1]^S \mid \forall \alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle \forall \beta \in \langle A_- \rangle: 0.25 \cdot v[\alpha] + 0.75 \cdot v[\beta] > 5/13\} .$$

In order to check whether $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_2 = 0$ holds, we need to determine $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\beta]$ for all $\beta \in \langle A_- \rangle$. We derive these values by considering the rules $A \xrightarrow{0.25} IA$ and $A \xrightarrow{0.75} ZA$. Since $\Upsilon_{>0}(v_0)[\beta] = 0$ for all $\beta \in \langle A_- \rangle$, we get $\Phi(F_0) \cap \text{Gen}_2 = 0$. Hence, Gen_2 can be removed from F_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 1 \ \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \notin \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 0 \\ F_1 &= [I] \leq 5/13 \ \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} \bigwedge_{\beta \in \langle A_- \rangle} 0.25 \cdot [\alpha] + 0.75 \cdot [\beta] \leq 5/13 \end{aligned}$$

Whereas in this iteration we refined the candidates for the 1-step reachability probabilities of all red and blue states, the next iteration additionally refines those for the configurations $\alpha \in \langle I_- \rangle$ depicted in orange. We skip the details of that iteration and depict the resulting frames instead:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 &= \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 1 \ \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \notin \langle F_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 0 \\ F_1 &= [I] \leq 5/13 \ \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} \bigwedge_{\beta \in \langle A_- \rangle} 0.25 \cdot [\alpha] + 0.75 \cdot [\beta] \leq 5/13 \\ &\quad \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} \bigwedge_{\beta \in \langle I_- \rangle} 0.25 \cdot [\alpha] + 0.25 \cdot 0.75 \cdot [\beta] \leq 5/13 \\ F_2 &= [I] \leq 5/13 \ \wedge \ \bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle F_- \rangle} \bigwedge_{\beta \in \langle A_- \rangle} 0.25 \cdot [\alpha] + 0.75 \cdot [\beta] \leq 5/13 \end{aligned}$$

The next iteration will reveal that F_1 is an inductive strengthening. In fact, by employing the presented generalization, we obtain an inductive strengthening after 3 iterations for all $\lambda = \text{Pr}^{c\Delta_2}(\diamond G) + c$ with $c > 0$. Without generalization, the number of required iterations grows ad infinitum.

Generalization can reduce the number of required iterations drastically. We believe that it is worthwhile to investigate the presented generalization technique further. For each summand of the form

$$\dots + p \cdot [a_1 \dots a_n] + \dots \tag{5.4}$$

with $a_1 \dots a_n \in \Gamma^*$ occurring in a constraint that is to be conjoined to some frame F_i (cf. Constraint 5.3), we try to generalize. We start with the coarsest generalization obtained from replacing Constraint 5.4 by

$$\bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle a_1 \dots a_{j-} \rangle} \dots + p \cdot [\alpha] + \dots$$

with $j = 1$. If conjoining this constraint to F_i violates relative inductiveness, we successively increase j until we find a generalization that does not violate relative inductiveness or until it holds that $j = n+1$ which means that this summand cannot be generalized.

Implementation-wise, we have to investigate how to employ SMT techniques to perform checks like $\Phi(F_1) \cap \text{Gen}_2 = \emptyset$ symbolically.

Furthermore, the above described generalization technique can be applied to the incremental, qualitative reachability analysis developed in Chapter 4.4. When executing $\text{IC3}[\mathbb{C}]$ on the presented example, we eventually conjoin the constraint

$$[ZAI] \doteq 0$$

to F_1 . Similar to the generalization from above, we can generalize this to

$$\bigwedge_{\alpha \in \langle Z_- \rangle} [\alpha] \doteq 0,$$

which suffices to find an inductive strengthening.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this thesis we have investigated whether the fundamental concepts of IC3—a symbolic model checking algorithm originally developed for reachability problems of finite transition systems—can be employed for model checking probabilistic systems. For that, we first studied these fundamental concepts. We developed a framework for solving reachability problems of possibly infinite and explicitly represented transition systems via IC3. Using this framework, we then developed IC3 for Markov chains. We provided an algorithm, proved its soundness and characterized its termination behavior. Furthermore, we extended IC3 for Markov chains by an incremental, *qualitative* reachability analysis for computing (sufficient subsets of) the set $S_{=0}$ of states that reach a goal state with probability 0 on-the-fly. We implemented our approach in Python and obtained experimental results. This evaluation shows that IC3 for *explicitly represented* Markov chains is not efficient. The main reason is that proceeding in an IC3-style fashion *without* generalization creates an overhead. Therefore, we discussed ideas on IC3 for—in some sense—symbolically represented Markov chains. In particular, we demonstrated that generalization in IC3 for Markov chains is possible and that it can reduce the number of required iterations drastically. Finally, we considered IC3 for *infinite* Markov chains. We demonstrated that our algorithm is suitable for model checking infinite-state Markov chains \mathcal{C} . However, termination cannot be guaranteed in general, even if $\Pr^{\mathcal{C}}(\diamond G) \neq \lambda$ holds. Finally, we presented ideas on how to obtain generalizations for Markov chains obtained from probabilistic pushdown automata.

Bibliography

- [BEKK13] Tomás Brázdil, Javier Esparza, Stefan Kiefer, and Antonín Kucera. Analyzing probabilistic pushdown automata. *Formal Methods in System Design*, 43(2):124–163, 2013.
- [BG15] Nikolaj Bjørner and Arie Gurfinkel. Property directed polyhedral abstraction. In *VMCAI*, volume 8931 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 263–281. Springer, 2015.
- [BK08] Christel Baier and Joost-Pieter Katoen. *Principles of model checking*. MIT Press, 2008.
- [Bra11] Aaron R. Bradley. Sat-based model checking without unrolling. In *VMCAI*, volume 6538 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 70–87. Springer, 2011.
- [Bra12] Aaron R. Bradley. Understanding IC3. In *SAT*, volume 7317 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 1–14. Springer, 2012.
- [BWB⁺11] Bettina Braitling, Ralf Wimmer, Bernd Becker, Nils Jansen, and Erika Ábrahám. Counterexample generation for markov chains using smt-based bounded model checking. In *FMOODS/FORTE*, volume 6722 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 75–89. Springer, 2011.
- [CG12] Alessandro Cimatti and Alberto Griggio. Software model checking via IC3. In *CAV*, volume 7358 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 277–293. Springer, 2012.
- [CGSS13] Alessandro Cimatti, Alberto Griggio, Bastiaan Joost Schaafsma, and Roberto Sebastiani. The mathsat5 SMT solver. In *TACAS*, volume 7795 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 93–107. Springer, 2013.
- [DJJL01] Pedro R. D’Argenio, Bertrand Jeannet, Henrik Ejersbo Jensen, and Kim Guldstrand Larsen. Reachability analysis of probabilistic systems by successive refinements. In *PAPM-PROBMIV*, volume 2165 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 39–56. Springer, 2001.
- [DJKV17] Christian Dehnert, Sebastian Junges, Joost-Pieter Katoen, and Matthias Volk. A storm is coming: A modern probabilistic model checker. In *CAV (2)*, volume 10427 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 592–600. Springer, 2017.

- [dMB08] Leonardo Mendonça de Moura and Nikolaj Bjørner. Z3: an efficient SMT solver. In *TACAS*, volume 4963 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 337–340. Springer, 2008.
- [EMB11] Niklas Eén, Alan Mishchenko, and Robert K. Brayton. Efficient implementation of property directed reachability. In *FMCAD*, pages 125–134. FMCAD Inc., 2011.
- [GKM14] Friedrich Gretz, Joost-Pieter Katoen, and Annabelle McIver. Operational versus weakest pre-expectation semantics for the probabilistic guarded command language. *Perform. Eval.*, 73:110–132, 2014.
- [GM15] Marco Gario and Andrea Micheli. PySMT: a solver-agnostic library for fast prototyping of smt-based algorithms. In *SMT Workshop*, 2015.
- [HB12] Krystof Hoder and Nikolaj Bjørner. Generalized property directed reachability. In *SAT*, volume 7317 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 157–171. Springer, 2012.
- [KEM06] Antonín Kucera, Javier Esparza, and Richard Mayr. Model checking probabilistic pushdown automata. *Logical Methods in Computer Science*, 2(1), 2006.
- [Kle14] Achim Klenke. *Probability theory: A comprehensive course*. 2014.
- [KNP12] Marta Z. Kwiatkowska, Gethin Norman, and David Parker. The PRISM benchmark suite. In *QEST*, pages 203–204. IEEE Computer Society, 2012.
- [Lan19] Tim Lange. *IC3 Software Model Checking*. PhD thesis, RWTH Aachen University, 2019.
- [LNN15] Tim Lange, Martin R. Neuhäuser, and Thomas Noll. IC3 software model checking on control flow automata. In *FMCAD*, pages 97–104. IEEE, 2015.
- [LNS82] Jean-Louis Lassez, V. L. Nguyen, and Liz Sonenberg. Fixed point theorems and semantics: A folk tale. *Inf. Process. Lett.*, 14(3):112–116, 1982.
- [MM05] Annabelle McIver and Carroll Morgan. *Abstraction, Refinement and Proof for Probabilistic Systems*. Monographs in Computer Science. Springer, 2005.
- [Par69] David Park. Fixpoint induction and proofs of program properties. *Machine Intelligence.*, 5, 1969.
- [pri] PRISM website: <http://prismmodelchecker.org>. Accessed: 2019-20-03.
- [Put94] Martin L. Puterman. *Markov Decision Processes: Discrete Stochastic Dynamic Programming*. John Wiley and Sons, 1994.
- [QK18] Tim Quatmann and Joost-Pieter Katoen. Sound value iteration. In *CAV (1)*, volume 10981 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 643–661. Springer, 2018.

-
- [Shm04] V. Shmatikov. Probabilistic model checking of an anonymity system. *Journal of Computer Security*, 12(3/4):355–377, 2004.
- [SS17] Tobias Seufert and Christoph Scholl. Sequential verification using reverse PDR. In *MBMV*, pages 79–90. Shaker Verlag, 2017.
- [WBB09] Ralf Wimmer, Bettina Braitleing, and Bernd Becker. Counterexample generation for discrete-time markov chains using bounded model checking. In *VMCAI*, volume 5403 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 366–380. Springer, 2009.